

Universitatea din Bucuresti Facultatea de Matematica si Informatica

Master: Baze de Date și Tehnologii Software

Proiect

Data Warehouse & Business Intelligence

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1. Modul Analiza

1.1 Descrierea modelului ales și a obiectivelor aplicației

Pentru realizarea acestui proiect am ales ca tema gestionarea unui lanț de sală de fitness în cadrul cărora se oferă servicii de antrenament precum și evidențierea rezultatelor la anumite intervale de timp.

Operațiunile din baza de date se concentrează asupra clienților. Aceștia au posibilitatea de a achiziționa abonamente cu durată și prețuri diferite. Fiecare sesiune de antrenament se realizează individual, cu sau fără îndrumarea unui antrenor de fitness.

În baza de date sunt stocate datele specifice antrenorilor, salile de sport unde aceștia lucrează precum și programele de fitness disponibile.

Utilitatea acestui model este aceea de monitorizare al rezultatelor, atât rezultatele clienților individuali dar și al lanțului de sală de fitness, întrucât se pot genera rapoarte rezultate/cost pentru clienți cât și rapoarte profit/costuri pentru lanțul de sală.

Baza de date conține 10 tabele. În cadrul acestora au fost aplicate 3 constrângeri, constrângerea PRIMARY KEY, constrângerea FOREIGN KEY și constrângerea Unique.

Constrângerea PRIMARY KEY identifică unic fiecare înregistrare. Astfel în fiecare din cele 10 tabele, există o coloană, prima coloană, definită PRIMARY KEY. Existența identificatorului unic la nivel de tabel permite operațiuni asupra oricărei înregistrări atunci când se dorește realizarea de operațiuni asupra acesteia și numai acesteia.

Constrângerea FOREIGN KEY stabilește o legătură pe baza unei chei externe între o coloană din tabel și o coloană din tabelul referit. În tabelele ce conțin date despre achiziții de servicii precum și rezultatele clienților, sunt folosite chei externe pentru a genera rapoarte individuale despre fiecare client.

Constrângerea UNIQUE asigură ca toate valorile dintr-o coloană sunt diferite.

1.2 Diagramele bazei de date OLTP

1.2.1. Diagrama entitate - relație a bazei de date OLTP

1.2.2. Diagrama conceptuală a bazei de date OLTP

1.3 Diagrama stea

1.4 Descrierea câmpurilor necesare pentru fiecare tabel din baza de date depozit și modul de populare al acestora cu informații din baza de date OLTP

Baza de date depozit este alcatuita din 5 tabele dimensiune si 2 tabele de fapte. Cele 5 tabele dimensiune sunt "Customers", "Trainers", "Subscriptions", "Time" si "Locations". Cele 2 tabele de fapte sunt "Subscriptions_History" si "Sessions_History".

Tabelul dimensiune "**Customers**" are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Id** - Primary Key - Identificator unic pentru fiecare inregistrare din tabelul dimensiune "Customers". **Autoincrementat** folosind secventa "tbdw_customers_seq".
- **Customer_id** - Identificator unic preluat din tabelul "Customers" din baza de date O.L.T.P., acesta reprezentand cheia primara a tabelului respectiv. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura "**tbdw_customers_insert**".

- **First_name** – Numele de familie al clientului, preluat din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.
- **Last_name** – Numele mic al clientului, preluat din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.
- **Email** – Identificator Unic – Adresa de email a clientului, preluata din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.
- **Phone_number** – Numarul de telefon al clientului, preluat din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.
- **Date_of_birth** – Data de nastere a clientului, preluata din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.
- **Gender** – Genul clientului, preluat din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.
- **Has_health_issues** – Variabila ce determina daca clientul poate achizitiona servicii cu sau fara antrenor. Preluata din tabelul “Customers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_customers_insert**”.

Tabelul dimensiune “**Trainers**” are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Id** – Primary Key – Identificator unic pentru fiecare inregistrare din tabelul dimensiune “Trainers”. **Autoincrementat** folosind secventa “**tbdw_trainers_seq**”.
- **Trainer_id** – Identificator unic preluat din tabelul Trainers din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **First_name** – Numele de familie al antrenorului, preluat din tabelul Trainers din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **Last_name** – Numele mic al antrenorului, preluat din tabelul “Trainers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **Email** – Adresa de email a antrenorului, preluata din tabelul “Trainers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **Phone_number** – Numarul de telefon al antrenorului, preluat din tabelul “Trainers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **Birth_date** – Data de nastere a antrenorului, preluata din tabelul “Trainers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **Hire_date** – Data de angajare a antrenorului, preluata din tabelul “Contracts” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.

- **Contract_end_date** – Data de incheiere a contractului antrenorului, preluata din tabelul “Contracts” din baza de data O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”.
- **Gender** – Genul antrenorului, preluat din tabelul “Trainers” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_trainers_insert**”

Tabelul dimensiune “**Subscriptions**” are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Id** – Primary Key – Identificator unic pentru fiecare inregistrare din tabelul dimensiune “Subscriptions”. **Autoincrementat** folosind secventa “tbdw_subscriptions_seq”.
- **Subscription_id** – Identificator unic preluat din tabelul “Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.
- **Max_number_sessions** – Variabila ce specifica numarul maxim de sesiuni disponibile din abonament, preluat din tabelul “Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.
- **Title** – Denumirea abonamentului, preluata din tabelul “Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.
- **Description** – Descrierea abonamentului, preluat din tabelul “Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.
- **With_trainer** – Variabila ce specifica daca abonamentul include antrenor personalizat. Un client care are probleme de sanatate nu va putea achizitiona abonamente decat daca acestea includ antrenor personalizat. Preluat din tabelul “Subscriptions”, transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.
- **Max_number_days** – Variabila specifica numarul maxim de zile de valabilitate ale abonamentului. Preluat din tabelul “Subscriptions”, transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “**tbdw_subscriptions_insert**”.

Tabelul dimensiune “**Time**” are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Timp_id** – Primary Key – Generat folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **An** – Anul, exprimat numeric, asociat datei stocate in variabila “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Extras folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Semestru** – Semestrul, exprimat numeric, asociat datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generat folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.

- **Trimestru** – Trimestrul, exprimat numeric, asociat datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generat folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Luna** – Luna, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata din variabila “timp_id” folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Saptamana_an** - Saptamana din an, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Saptamana_luna** – Saptamana din luna, exprimata numeric asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Zi_an** – Ziua din an, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata din variabila “timp_id” folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Zi_luna** – Ziua din luna, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Zi_saptamana** – Ziua din saptamana, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Zi_nume** – Ziua din saptamana, exprimata prin denumire, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Luna_nume** – Luna din an, exprimata prin denumire, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Weekend** – Variabila utilizata pentru a specifica daca ziua asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” este considerata zi de week-end, prin valoarea 1, sau nu prin valoarea 0. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **An_bisect** – Variabila utilizata pentru a specifica daca anul asociat datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” este considerat an bisect, prin valoarea 1, sa nu prin valoarea 0. Generat folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Saptamana_calendar** – Saptamana calendaristica, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.
- **Saptamana_an_business** – Saptamana din an, exprimata numeric, asociata datei stocate in coloana “timp_id” din tabelul dimensiune “Time”. Generata folosind procedura “**tbdw_time_insert**”.

Tabelul dimensiune “**Locations**” are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Id** - Primary Key – Identificator unic pentru fiecare inregistrare din tabelul dimensiune “Locations”. **Autoincrementat** folosind secventa “tbdw_locations_seq”.
- **Location_id** – Identificator unic preluat din tabelul “Locations” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”.
- **Capacity** – Coloana ce specifica numarul maxim de clienti ce pot sa utilizeze sala de fitness in acelasi timp. Valoare preluata din tabelul “Locations” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”
- **State_name** – Numele judetului in care se afla locatia salii de fitness, preluata din tabelul “States” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”.
- **City_name** – Numele orasului in care se afla locatia salii de fitness, preluata din tabelul “Cities” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”.
- **Address** – Adresa salii de fitness, preluata din tabelul “Locations” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”
- **City_id** – Identificatorul ID din baza de date O.L.T.P. al orasului in care se afla locatia salii de fitness, preluat din tabelul “Cities” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”.
- **State_id** – Identificatorul ID din baza de date O.L.T.P. al judetului in care se afla locatia sali de fitness din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_locations_insert”.

Tabelul de fapte “**Subscriptions_History**” are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Id** - Primary Key – Identificator unic pentru fiecare inregistrare din tabelul de fapte “Subscriptions_History”. **Autoincrementat** folosind secventa “tbdw_subscriptions_seq”.
- **Subscription_id** – Foreign Key – Identificator preluat din tabelul “Customers_Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabellele “Subscriptions_History” si “Subscriptions” din DW. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert”.
- **Customer_Subscription_id** – Identificator unic preluat din tabelul “Customers_Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert”.
- **Customer_id** – Foreign Key - Identificator preluat din tabelul “Customers_Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabellele “Subscriptions_History” si “Customers” din DW. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert”.
- **Start_time_id** – Foreign Key - Data de la care abonamentul intra in vigoare. Preluata din tabelul “Customers_Subscriptions”. Permite legatura intre tabellele

“Subscriptions_history” si “Time”. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert](#)”

- **End_time_id** – Foreign Key – Ultima zi de valabilitate a abonamentului. Preluata in tabelul “Customers_Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabelele “Subscriptions_History” si “Time” Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert](#)”
- **Price** – Pretul abonamentului la momentul achizitiei, preluat din tabelul “Subscriptions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert](#)”

Tabelul de fapte “Sessions_History” are urmatoarele campuri:

- **Id** – Primary Key – Identificator unic pentru fiecare inregistrare din tabelul de fapte “Sessions_History”. **Autoincrementat** folosind secventa “[tbdw_sessions_seq](#)”.
- **Session_id** – Identificator unic preluat din tabelul “Sessions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_sessions_history_insert](#)”.
- **Customer_id** – Foreign Key - Identificator preluat din tabelul “Sessions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabelele “Sessions_History” si “Customers” din DW. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_sessions_history_insert](#)”.
- **Trainer_id** – Foreign Key - Identificator preluat din tabelul “Sessions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabelele “Sessions_History” si “Trainers” din DW. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_sessions_history_insert](#)”.
- **Location_id** - Foreign Key - Identificator preluat din tabelul “Sessions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabelele “Sessions_History” si “Locations” din DW. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_sessions_history_insert](#)”.
- **Customer_Subscription_id** - Foreign Key - Identificator preluat din tabelul “Sessions” din baza de date O.L.T.P. Permite legatura intre tabelele “Sessions_History” si “Subscriptions_History” din DW. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_sessions_history_insert](#)”.
- **Start_time_id** - Data la care clientul a inceput o sesiune de antrenament. Preluata din tabelul “Sessions”. Transferul se realizeaza folosind procedura “[tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert](#)”.
-

1.5 Identificarea constrângerilor specifice depozitelor de date ce trebuie definite, justificând alegerea făcută

Intr-o baza de date Data Warehouse, constrangerile de tip primary key sau unique pot fi definite cu doua proprietati suplimentare. Prima proprietate poate fi “enable” sau “disable”, iar a doua proprietate “ validated” sau “not validated”.

Utilizand aceste proprietati se pot obtine 4 rezultate diferite.

1. “Enabled Validated” va utiliza constrangerea si se va asigura ca fiecare operatie respecta constrangerea respectiva.
2. “Enabled Not Validated” se va utiliza constrangerea iar toate operatiile noi se vor executa in conformitate cu aceasta, insa datele deja existente nu vor fi verificate de aceasta.
3. “Disabled Validated” constrangerea nu se aplica pe operatiile noi insa datele existente respecta regulile impuse de constrangere
4. “Disabled Not Validated” constrangerea nu se aplica pe operatiile noi iar datele existente nu au fost verificate daca respecta regulile impuse de constrangere.

Pentru fiecare tabel din D.W., **Trainers**, **Customers**, **Locations**, **Subscriptions**, **Subscriptions_history**, **Sessions_history** vom defini cate o constrangere de tip **UNIQUE** avand proprietatile “**disable validate**”.

Pentru **tabelul de timp** din D.W., “**Time**”, vom aplica proprietatile “disable validate” pe cheia primara “**timp_id**”.

Aceste constrangeri, definite cu proprietatile “disable validate” vor avea in baza de date index-ul “null” astfel incat operatiile de tip insert, update si delete nu vor putea fi executate pe aceste tabele.

Vom modifica constrangerile acestor proprietati din “disable validate” in “enable” atunci cand dorim sa introducem date noi in Data Warehouse sau cand dorim sa facem alte tipuri de modificari. Si le vom modifica inapoi din “enable” in “disable validate” atunci cand dorim sa nu mai permitem executarea acestor operatii in tabele.

Aceste proprietati sunt esentiale intr-o baza de date Data Warehouse pentru a asigura integritatea datelor.

La nivelul D.W. se vor defini si alte constrangeri de chei primare si alte chei “unique”. De exemplu pentru fiecare tabel cu exceptia tabelului “Time”, va exista campul “id”, definit “Primary Key”. Valorile implicite pentru acest camp vor fi “enable validate norely”.

1.6 Identificarea indecșilor specifici depozitelor de date ce trebuie definiți asupra modelului; formularea unei cereri în limbaj natural care va determina utilizarea indecșilor specificați și va fi implementată în următoarea etapă

1.6.1 Exemplu index de tip BITMAP

“Sa se obtina numarul de client exprimat in procente ce au probleme de sanatate.”

In baza de date, folosim coloana “has_health_issues” din tabelul “Customers” pentru a determina daca un client are probleme de sanatate sau nu. In cazul in care clientul are probleme de sanatate, acesta nu poate achizitiona un abonament ce nu necesita prezenta unui antrenor personal.

In coloana “has_health_issues” vom avea valorile “0” in cazul in care clientul nu are probleme de sanatate si valoarea “1” daca acesta are problem de sanatate.

Deoarece vorbim de o situatie in care avem cardinalitate mica, vom folosi un index de tip BITMAP. Vom analiza si comparara costurile unei astfel de interogari cu si fara utilizarea index-ului de tip BITMAP.

1.7 Identificarea obiectelor de tip dimensiune ce trebuie definite asupra modelului

Vom defini obiecte de tip dimensiune pentru tabelele “Locations” si “Time” din D.W.

Pentru tabelul “Locations”, obiectul de tip dimensiune va contine o ierarhie pentru coloanele (id, city_name, state_name) prin care asociem relatii ONE to MANY pentru acesta si un atribut pentru coloanele (“address” si “capacity”) prin care asociem relatii ONE to ONE intre acestea si locatie.

Pentru tabelul “Time” obiectul de tip dimensiune va contine doua ierarhii. Acestea se vor defini pentru coloanele (timp_id, saptamana_luna, luna, trimestru,semestru,an) prin care asociem relatii ONE to MANY pentru acestea.

1.8 Identificarea tabelor care vor fi partiționate și a tipului de partiționare; formularea unei cereri în limbaj natural care va determina utilizarea lor și va fi implementată în următoarea etapă

1.8.1 Exemplu partitionare de tip “Range”

Se doreste obtinerea numarului de sesiuni realizate per an, din ultimii 10 ani de zile.

Se va implementa o partitionare de tip “Range” asupra tabelului “Sessions_History”.

1.9 Formularea în limbaj natural a unei cereri SQL complexe care va fi optimizată în următoarea etapă, folosind tehnici specifice bazelor de date depozit. Precizarea tehnicilor de optimizare ce ar putea fi utilizate pentru această cerere particulară (avantaje / dezavantaje de utilizare pentru o anumită tehnică)

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

1. 10 Formularea în limbaj natural a cel puțin 5 cereri, specifice DW, cu grad de complexitate diferit, concretizate în rapoarte (grafice) ce vor fi create în următoarele etape.

1.10.1 Exemplul 1

1. Sa se verifice daca capacitatea locatiilor a fost depasita. Daca aceasta a fost depasita, sa se afiseze, ziua in care a fost depasita, numele locatiei, judetul, si numarul de sesiuni inregistrate in ziua respectiva. Sa se ordoneze rezultatele in functie de adresa, judet, data si capacitate. Sa se determine costul interogarii.

2. Sa se modifice cererea anterioara astfel incat sa se afiseze locatiile in care capacitatea a fost depasita cu minim 50%. Datele vor fi ordonate in functie de locatie.

3. Pentru locatiile obtinute la punctul anterior sa se determine daca exista un trend ascendent in ultimii 5 ani de zile de crestere al numarului de sesiuni. Sa se ordoneze rezultatele in functie de locatie, an, numarul de sesiuni din anul respectiv.

1.10.2 Exemplul 2

Sa se afiseze numarul de clienti care prefera sesiuni de antrenament cu antrenori de sex masculin si numarul de clienti care prefera sesiuni de antrenament cu antrenori de sex feminin.

1.10.3 Exemplul 3

Sa se calculeze veniturile din ultimii 10 ani de zile. Sa se afiseze anul si suma totala a incasarilor. Sa se ordoneze dupa an, descrescator.

2. Modul BACK-END

2.1. Crearea bazei de date OLTP și a utilizatorilor

```
create table tb_trainers (trainer_id Int,first_name Varchar2(100),last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50),birth_date Date,gender Varchar2 (25));

create table tb_customers (customer_id Int,first_name Varchar2(100),last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50), date_of_birth Date,gender Varchar2(20), has_health_issues Number(1) default 0);

create table tb_results (result_id int,customer_id int, body_fat Number(3),weight Number(3), Number(3),age int,entry_date Date);

create table tb_customers_subscriptions (customer_subscription_id int,subscription_id int, customer_id int,price Number(6),start_date Date,
end_date Date);

create table tb_subscriptions (subscription_id Number(6),max_number_sessions int, sb_title Varchar2 (256),sb_description Varchar2 (1024),
with_trainer Number(1) default 0,max_number_days int, number(6));

create table tb_sessions (session_id Int,customer_id int,customer_subscription_id Int, location_id Int,trainer_id Int,start_date Date);

create table tb_locations (location_id int,location_capacity int,city_id int,address Varchar2 (256));

create table tb_contracts (contract_id int,trainer_id int,start_date Date,end_date Date, salary Number(10));

create table tb_states (state_id int,state_name Varchar2 (256));

create table tb_cities (city_id int,state_id int,city_name Varchar2 (256));

create table tbe_first_names (first_id int,first_name varchar (100),gender varchar (50));

create table tbe_last_names (last_id int,last_name varchar (100));

create table tbe_health (health_id int,health_value int);
```


Am creat cele 10 tabelle ale bazei de date OLTP, precum si 3 tabelle suplimentare. Cele 3 tabelle suplimentare vor fi utilizate de scripturile de generare a datelor pentru tabellele bazei de date OLTP.

```

alter session set "_ORACLE_SCRIPT"=true;

create user dwbi_oltp identified by dwbi_oltp_password password expire;
grant create session to dwbi_oltp;

select username, authentication_type, account_status, expiry_date, created
from dba_users
order by created desc;

create profile dwbi_oltp_employees limit
  cpu_per_call 9000
  sessions_per_user 1
  password_life_time 7
  failed_login_attempts 5;

alter user dwbi_oltp account unlock;
alter user dwbi_oltp identified by dwbi_oltp_password;

alter user dwbi_oltp profile dwbi_oltp_employees;

select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like 'dwbi_%';

grant select on tb_customers to dwbi_oltp;
grant select on tb_customers_subscriptions to dwbi_oltp;
grant select on tb_subscriptions to dwbi_oltp;

grant insert on tb_customers to dwbi_oltp;
grant insert on tb_customers_subscriptions to dwbi_oltp;

grant update on tb_customers to dwbi_oltp;

SELECT * FROM DBA_TAB_PRIVS where lower(table_name) like 'tb_%';

```

Este creat utilizatorul “dwbi_oltp” cu parola “dwbi_oltp_password” si I se da drepturi de “create session”.

Se creaza profiluri de utilizatori pentru utilizatorii O.L.T.P avand consumul de CPU per apel sa nu depaseasca 90 secunde, sa aiba dreptul la o singura sesiune la un moment dat, timpul de viata al unei parole sa fie de 30 de zile si sa poata gresi parola de maxim 5 ori.

Utilizatorul “dwbi_oltp” primește drepturi de select asupra tabelelor “Customers”, “Subscriptions” și “Customers_Subscriptions”, drepturi de insert asupra tabelelor “Customers” și “Customers_Subscriptions” și drepturi de actualizare date asupra tabelului “Customers”.

Utilizatorul “dwbi_oltp” va fi utilizat la nivelul aplicației front-end.

2.2 Generarea datelor și inserarea acestora în tabele

Instructiuni de autoincrementare PK pentru OLTP

```
CREATE SEQUENCE tb_trainers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers MODIFY trainer_id int DEFAULT tb_trainers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_customers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_customers MODIFY customer_id int DEFAULT tb_customers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_results_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_results MODIFY result_id int DEFAULT tb_results_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_customers_subscriptions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions MODIFY customer_subscription_id int DEFAULT tb_customers_subscriptions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_subscriptions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_subscriptions MODIFY subscription_id int DEFAULT tb_subscriptions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_sessions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions MODIFY session_id int DEFAULT tb_sessions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_locations_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_locations MODIFY location_id int DEFAULT tb_locations_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tb_contracts_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_contracts MODIFY contract_id int DEFAULT tb_contracts_seq.nextval NOT NULL;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE tb_cities_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tb_cities MODIFY city_id int DEFAULT tb_cities_seq.nextval NOT NULL;
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with a query window containing the following SQL statements:

```
108 CREATE SEQUENCE tb_locations_seq START WITH 1;
109 ALTER TABLE tb_locations MODIFY location_id int DEFAULT tb_locations_seq.nextval NOT NULL;
110
111 CREATE SEQUENCE tb_contracts_seq START WITH 1;
112 ALTER TABLE tb_contracts MODIFY contract_id int DEFAULT tb_contracts_seq.nextval NOT NULL;
113
114 CREATE SEQUENCE tb_cities_seq START WITH 1;
115 ALTER TABLE tb_cities MODIFY city_id int DEFAULT tb_cities_seq.nextval NOT NULL;
116
```

The Script Output window shows the following results:

```
Task completed in 0.309 seconds
Table TB_SESSIONS altered.
Sequence TB_LOCATIONS_SEQ created.
Table TB_LOCATIONS altered.
Sequence TB_CONTRACTS_SEQ created.
Table TB_CONTRACTS altered.
Sequence TB_CITIES_SEQ created.
Table TB_CITIES altered.
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with a query window containing the following SQL statement:

```
117 select sequence_name from dba_sequences
118 where sequence_name like 'TB_%';
119
```

The Query Result window shows the following output:

SEQUENCE_NAME
1 TB_CITIES_SEQ
2 TB_CONTRACTS_SEQ
3 TB_CUSTOMERS_SEQ
4 TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_SEQ
5 TB_LOCATIONS_SEQ
6 TB_RESULTS_SEQ
7 TB_SESSIONS_SEQ
8 TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS_SEQ
9 TB_TRAINERS_SEQ

Popularea celor 3 tabele suplimentare. Acestea contin nume de persoane. Datele vor fi folosite pentru a genera nume aleatorii de antrenori si clienti.

```
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 1, 1);
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 2, 0);
...
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 8, 0);
INSERT INTO tbe_health VALUES ( 9, 0);

INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 1, 'Oliver', 'male');
```

```

INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 2, 'Emma', 'female');
...
INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 39, 'Logan', 'male');
INSERT INTO tbe_first_names VALUES ( 40, 'Nicole', 'female');

INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 1, 'Green');
INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 2, 'Hall');
...
INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 19, 'Morgan');
INSERT INTO tbe_last_names VALUES ( 20, 'Carter');

```


Inserare date tabel tb_trainers

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_trainers_insert AS
  t_first_name tb_trainers.first_name%TYPE;
  t_last_name tb_trainers.last_name%TYPE;
  t_email tb_trainers.email%TYPE;
  t_phone_number tb_trainers.phone_number%TYPE;
  t_birth_date tb_trainers.birth_date%TYPE;
  t_gender tb_trainers.gender%TYPE;
  t_max_number number;
  t_count_number number;
  t_rand_choice1 number;
  t_rand_choice2 number;
  t_last_id tb_trainers.trainer_id%TYPE;
BEGIN
  t_max_number := 438;
  t_count_number := 1;

  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
  Loop

    t_rand_choice1 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,40));
    SELECT first_name, gender into t_first_name, t_gender FROM tbe_first_names where first_id = t_rand_choice1;

    t_rand_choice2 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,20));
    SELECT last_name into t_last_name FROM tbe_last_names where last_id = t_rand_choice2;

    t_email := CONCAT(t_first_name, t_last_name);
    t_email := CONCAT(t_email,l_counter);
    t_email := CONCAT(t_email,'@t.dwbi.com');

    t_phone_number := CONCAT(TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)),TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)));
    t_phone_number := CONCAT(t_phone_number,TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1000,9999)));

    SELECT TO_DATE(
      TRUNC(
        DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '1971-01-01','J')
          ,TO_CHAR(DATE '2000-01-01','J')
        )
      ),'J'
    ) into t_birth_date FROM DUAL;
    INSERT INTO tb_trainers
      (
        first_name,
        last_name,
        email,
        phone_number,
        birth_date,
        gender
      )
    VALUES
      (
        t_first_name,
        t_last_name,
        t_email,
        t_phone_number,
        t_birth_date,
        t_gender
      );
  END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
```

```

begin
tb_trainers_insert;
end;

```


The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The Connections pane on the left displays the database structure, including the 'TBE_FIRST_NAMES' table. The Worksheet contains the following PL/SQL code:

```

begin
  t_birth_date,
  t_gender
);
END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_trainers_insert;
end;

```

The Script Output window shows the execution results:

```

1 row inserted.

Procedure TB_TRAINERS_INSERT compiled

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

```


The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The Connections pane on the left displays the database structure, including the 'tb_trainers' table. The Worksheet contains the following SQL query:

```

select * from tb_trainers order by trainer_id desc;

```

The Query Result window shows the following data:

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	GENDER
1	Lydia	Bates	LydiaBates438@t.dvbi.com	1646485165	17-NOV-80	female
2	Ryan	Green	RyanGreen437@t.dvbi.com	3217194227	28-NOV-96	male
3	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes436@t.dvbi.com	5567697233	24-NOV-72	male
4	Hannah	Bates	HannahBates435@t.dvbi.com	3827499419	21-AUG-84	female
5	Julia	Palmer	JuliaPalmer434@t.dvbi.com	7103692916	21-APR-75	female
6	Elaine	Brooks	ElaineBrooks433@t.dvbi.com	2179821244	09-JUN-92	female
7	Elaine	Hughes	ElaineHughes432@t.dvbi.com	3644255049	11-MAY-73	female
8	Louis	Holmes	LouisHolmes431@t.dvbi.com	2242239332	11-SEP-77	male
9	Charles	Cooper	CharlesCooper430@t.dvbi.com	8117552651	06-NOV-59	male
10	Vivian	Andrews	VivianAndrews429@t.dvbi.com	5305323821	07-SEP-97	female
11	Hannah	Ross	HannahRoss428@t.dvbi.com	4549964990	15-MAR-80	female
12	Logan	Clarke	LoganClarke427@t.dvbi.com	6445982255	29-APR-81	male
13	Amanda	Shepard	AmandaShepard426@t.dvbi.com	9371863563	13-AUG-95	female
14	Louis	Stevens	LouisStevens425@t.dvbi.com	8377578513	05-APR-80	male
15	Alice	Shepard	AliceShepard424@t.dvbi.com	6271273661	26-MAY-76	female
16	Heien	Stevens	HeienStevens423@t.dvbi.com	7799049475	06-APR-84	female
17	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes422@t.dvbi.com	2858469512	27-JUL-98	male
18	Oscar	Brooks	OscarBrooks421@t.dvbi.com	9165024439	23-OCT-72	male
19	Elizabeth	Hopkins	ElizabethHopkins420@t.dvbi.com	9033546619	28-JAN-85	female
20	Marissa	Ross	MarissaRoss419@t.dvbi.com	3125634380	16-NOV-86	female

Inserare date tabel tb_customers

```

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_customers_insert AS
  t_first_name tb_customers.first_name%TYPE;

```

```

t_last_name tb_customers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tb_customers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tb_customers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_date_of_birth tb_customers.date_of_birth%TYPE;
t_gender tb_customers.gender%TYPE;
t_has_health_issues tb_customers.has_health_issues%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_rand_choice1 number;
t_rand_choice2 number;
t_rand_choice3 number;
BEGIN
  t_max_number := 3872;
  t_count_number := 1;

  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
  Loop

    t_rand_choice1 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,40));
    SELECT first_name, gender into t_first_name, t_gender FROM tbe_first_names where first_id = t_rand_choice1;

    t_rand_choice2 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,20));
    SELECT last_name into t_last_name FROM tbe_last_names where last_id = t_rand_choice2;

    t_email := CONCAT(t_first_name, t_last_name);
    t_email := CONCAT(t_email,l_counter);
    t_email := CONCAT(t_email,'@c.dwbi.com');

    t_phone_number := CONCAT(TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)),TRUNC(dbms_random.value(100,999)));
    t_phone_number := CONCAT(t_phone_number,TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1000,9999)));

    SELECT TO_DATE(
      TRUNC(
        DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '1961-01-01','J')
          ,TO_CHAR(DATE '2012-01-01','J')
        )
      ),'J'
    ) into t_date_of_birth FROM DUAL;

    t_rand_choice3 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,9));
    SELECT health_value into t_has_health_issues FROM tbe_health where health_id = t_rand_choice3;

    INSERT INTO tb_customers
      (
        first_name,
        last_name,
        email,
        phone_number ,
        date_of_birth,
        gender,
        has_health_issues
      )
    VALUES
      (
        t_first_name,
        t_last_name,
        t_email,
        t_phone_number,
        t_date_of_birth,
        t_gender,
        t_has_health_issues
      );
  END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;

```

```

begin
tb_customers_insert;
end;

```


Inserare date tabel tb_subscriptions

insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (1,'1 Intrate Spa', 'În saloanele de spa din zilele noastre primesti tratamente de îngrijire faciala si corporala, diverse tipuri de masaj, sauna, aromoterapie,

cromoterapie, terapie prin pietre, dusuri, împachetari cu plante, bai în piscina, tratamente anticelulitice si antivergeturi',1,1,60);
insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (1,'1 Intrare piscina copii', 'Oferta valabila pentru copii cu varstele cuprinse între 10-16 ani',1,1,30);
insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (1,'1 Intrare Sala Fitness', 'Oferta include acces la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutate pentru a antrena fiecare zona de musculatura corpului ',0,1,35);
 ...
insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (12,'Pachet lunar fitness cu antrenor', 'Oferta include 12 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate într-un interval de 31 de zile. Antrenamentul se desfasoara cu antrenor',1,31,720);
insert into tb_subscriptions (max_number_sessions,sb_title,sb_description,with_trainer,max_number_days,price) values (16,'Pachet 2 luni fitness cu antrenor', 'Oferta include 16 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate într-un interval de 60 de zile. Antrenamentul se desfasoara cu antrenor',1,60,880);

Inserare date tabel tb_customers_subscriptions

```

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_customers_subscriptions_insert AS
  t_subscription_id tb_customers_subscriptions.subscription_id%TYPE;
  t_customer_id tb_customers_subscriptions.customer_id%TYPE;
  t_start_date tb_customers_subscriptions.start_date%TYPE;
  t_end_date tb_customers_subscriptions.end_date%TYPE;
  t_price tb_customers_subscriptions.price%TYPE;
  t_max_number number;
  t_count_number number;
  t_rand_choice1 number;
  t_rand_choice2 int;
  t_duration number;
  t_required_trainer tb_customers.has_health_issues%type;

BEGIN
  t_max_number := 15000;
  t_count_number := 1;

  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
  Loop

    t_rand_choice1 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,3872));

    select has_health_issues into t_required_trainer from tb_customers where customer_id = t_rand_choice1;
  
```

```

if t_required_trainer = 1 then
  SELECT subscription_id
  INTO t_rand_choice2
  FROM tb_subscriptions
  where with_trainer = 1
  ORDER BY DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE
  FETCH FIRST ROW ONLY;
else
  SELECT subscription_id
  INTO t_rand_choice2
  FROM tb_subscriptions
  ORDER BY DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE
  FETCH FIRST ROW ONLY;
end if;

t_customer_id := t_rand_choice1;
t_subscription_id := t_rand_choice2;

SELECT price into t_price from tb_subscriptions where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;
SELECT max_number_days into t_duration from tb_subscriptions where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;

t_duration := t_duration - 1;

SELECT TO_DATE(
  TRUNC(
    DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '2000-01-01','J')
      ,TO_CHAR(DATE '2023-02-12','J')
    )
  ),'J'
) into t_start_date FROM DUAL;

t_end_date := t_start_date + t_duration;

--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_subscription_id:'||t_subscription_id);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_customer_id:'||t_customer_id);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_start_date:'||t_start_date);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_end_date:'||t_end_date);
--DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_price:'||t_price);

INSERT INTO tb_customers_subscriptions
(
  subscription_id,
  customer_id,
  start_date,
  end_date,
  price
)
VALUES
(
  t_subscription_id,
  t_customer_id,
  t_start_date,
  t_end_date,
  t_price
);

-- DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_required_trainer:'||t_required_trainer);
-- DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('t_subscription_id:'||t_subscription_id);

END Loop;
END;
/
set serveroutput on;

```

```

begin
tb_customers_subscriptions_insert;
end;

```


Inserire date table tb_states si tb_cities

```

insert into tb_states values (1,'Alba');
insert into tb_states values (2,'Arad');
...
insert into tb_states values (41,'Valcea');

```

```
insert into tb_states values (42,'Vrancea');
```

```
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (1,'Alba Iulia');
```

```
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (1,'Sebes');
```

...

```
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (42,'Jaristea');
```

```
insert into tb_cities (state_id,city_name) values (42,'Ploscuteni');
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with a query window titled 'Query Builder'. The query contains several insert statements for the 'tb_cities' table, including one for state 42. The 'Script Output' window shows the execution results: 'Task completed in 5.659 seconds' and '1 row inserted.' repeated three times. The 'Connections' pane on the left shows the database schema, including tables like 'TBE_FIRST_NAMES' and 'TBE_HEALTH'.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with a query window titled 'Query Builder'. The query contains a select statement to count the number of rows in 'tb_states' and 'tb_cities'. The 'Script Output' window shows the execution results: 'All Rows Fetched: 2 in 0.005 seconds' and a table with 2 rows and 2 columns: 'TABLE_NAME' and 'COUNT'. The 'Connections' pane on the left shows the database schema, including tables like 'TBE_FIRST_NAMES' and 'TBE_HEALTH'.

TABLE_NAME	COUNT
tb_states	42
tb_cities	840

Inserare date tabel tb_locations

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_locations_insert AS
  t_location_capacity tb_locations.location_capacity%TYPE;
  t_city_id tb_locations.city_id%TYPE;
  t_address tb_locations.address%TYPE;
  t_max_number number;
  t_count_number number;
  t_rand_choice number;
  t_rand_choice2 number;
BEGIN
  t_max_number := 70;
  t_count_number := 1;

  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
  Loop

    t_location_capacity := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(50,100));

    t_rand_choice2 := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,840));
    SELECT city_id into t_city_id FROM tb_cities where city_id = t_rand_choice2;

    t_rand_choice := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(10000,100000));
    t_address := CONCAT('address',t_rand_choice);

    INSERT INTO tb_locations
      (
        location_capacity,
        city_id,
        address
      )
    VALUES
      (
        t_location_capacity,
        t_city_id,
        t_address
      );
  END Loop;
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tb_locations_insert;
end;
```


Inserare date tabel tb_contracts

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_contracts_insert AS

```
t_trainer_id tb_contracts.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_start_date tb_contracts.start_date%TYPE;
t_end_date tb_contracts.end_date%TYPE;
t_salary tb_contracts.salary%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_rand_choice1 number;
t_rand_choice2 number;
t_duration number;
```

BEGIN

```
select count(*) into t_max_number from tb_trainers;
t_count_number := 1;
```

```
for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
```

Loop

```
t_trainer_id := l_counter;
```

```
t_rand_choice1 := Trunc(dbms_random.value(15,45));
```

```
t_rand_choice2 := t_rand_choice1 * 100;
```

```
t_salary := t_rand_choice2;
```

```
SELECT TO_DATE(  
  TRUNC(  
    DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(TO_CHAR(DATE '2000-01-01','J')  
                      ,TO_CHAR(DATE '2023-02-12','J')  
                      )  
  ),'J'  
) into t_start_date FROM DUAL;
```

```
t_end_date := add_months(t_start_date, trunc(DBMS_RANDOM.VALUE(1,72)));
```

```
INSERT INTO tb_contracts
```

```
(  
  trainer_id,  
  start_date,  
  end_date,  
  salary  
)
```

```
VALUES
```

```
(  
  t_trainer_id,  
  t_start_date,  
  t_end_date,  
  t_salary  
);
```

```
END Loop;
```

```
END;
```

```
set serveroutput on;
```

```
begin
```

```
tb_contracts_insert;
```

```
end;
```


Inserare date tabel tb_sessions

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tb_sessions_insert AS

```

t_customer_id tb_sessions.customer_id%TYPE;
t_customer_subscription_id tb_sessions.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_location_id tb_sessions.location_id%TYPE;
t_trainer_id tb_sessions.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_start_date tb_sessions.start_date%TYPE;
t_max_number_sessions tb_subscriptions.max_number_sessions%TYPE;
t_unique_customer_subscription_id tb_sessions.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_rand_number_sessions number;
t_sessions_counter number;
t_required_trainer tb_customers.has_health_issues%type;

```

```

BEGIN

    BEGIN
        SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_count_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by
customer_subscription_id asc;
        SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_max_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by
customer_subscription_id desc;
    EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
        t_count_number := 0;
        t_max_number := 0;
    END;

    t_transfers := 0;
    t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
    dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Subscriptions in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

        t_customer_subscription_id := l_counter;

        BEGIN
            select max_number_sessions into t_max_number_sessions from tb_subscriptions tb1, tb_customers_subscriptions tb2
            where tb1.subscription_id = tb2.subscription_id and tb2.customer_subscription_id = l_counter;
        EXCEPTION
        WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
            t_max_number_sessions := null;
        END;

    if t_max_number_sessions = 1 then
        BEGIN
            select customer_subscription_id into t_unique_customer_subscription_id from tb_sessions where customer_subscription_id =
t_customer_subscription_id;
        EXCEPTION
        WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
            t_unique_customer_subscription_id := null;
        END;

        IF t_unique_customer_subscription_id is null THEN

            select customer_id, start_date
            into t_customer_id, t_start_date
            from tb_customers_subscriptions
            where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

            select has_health_issues into t_required_trainer from tb_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;

            if t_required_trainer = 1 then
                t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,438));
            else
                t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(0,438));
                if t_trainer_id = 0 then
                    t_trainer_id := null;
                end if;
            end if;

            t_location_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,70));

            INSERT INTO tb_sessions
            (
                customer_id,
                customer_subscription_id,
                location_id,
                trainer_id,
```

```

        start_date
    )
VALUES
    (
        t_customer_id,
        t_customer_subscription_id,
        t_location_id,
        t_trainer_id,
        t_start_date
    );
    t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
END IF;
t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

if t_max_number_sessions > 1 then

t_rand_number_sessions := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,t_max_number_sessions));
t_sessions_counter := 0;

for l_counter2 in t_sessions_counter..t_rand_number_sessions
Loop

select customer_id, start_date
into t_customer_id, t_start_date
from tb_customers_subscriptions
where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

select has_health_issues into t_required_trainer from tb_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;

if t_required_trainer = 1 then
t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,438));
else
t_trainer_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(0,438));
if t_trainer_id = 0 then
t_trainer_id := null;
end if;
end if;

t_location_id := TRUNC(dbms_random.value(1,70));

INSERT INTO tb_sessions
(
customer_id,
customer_subscription_id,
location_id,
trainer_id,
start_date
)
VALUES
(
t_customer_id,
t_customer_subscription_id,
t_location_id,
t_trainer_id,
t_start_date
);
t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;

end loop;

end if;

END Loop;

```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Sessions added.');
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

```
END;
```

```
/
```



```
set serveroutput on;
```

```
begin
```

```
tb_sessions_insert;
```

```
end;
```


Afisare count() pentru cele 10 tabele din OLTP*

```

select 'tb_trainers', count(*) "COUNT" from tb_trainers
union all
select 'tb_customers', count(*) from tb_customers
union all
select 'tb_subscriptions', count(*) from tb_subscriptions
union all
select 'tb_customers_subscriptions', count(*) from tb_customers_subscriptions
union all
select 'tb_states', count(*) from tb_states
union all
select 'tb_cities', count(*) from tb_cities
union all
select 'tb_locations', count(*) from tb_locations
union all
select 'tb_contracts', count(*) from tb_contracts
union all
select 'tb_sessions', count(*) from tb_sessions
union all
select 'tb_results', count(*) from tb_results;

```

The screenshot displays the SQL Developer interface. The main window shows a query in the Query Builder:

```

union all
select 'tb_customers_subscriptions', count(*) from tb_customers_subscriptions
union all
select 'tb_states', count(*) from tb_states
union all
select 'tb_cities', count(*) from tb_cities
union all
select 'tb_locations', count(*) from tb_locations
union all
select 'tb_contracts', count(*) from tb_contracts
union all
select 'tb_sessions', count(*) from tb_sessions
union all
select 'tb_results', count(*) from tb_results;

```

The Query Result pane shows the following data:

TABLE_NAME	COUNT
1 tb_trainers	438
2 tb_customers	3672
3 tb_subscriptions	20
4 tb_customers_subscriptions	15000
5 tb_states	42
6 tb_cities	840
7 tb_locations	70
8 tb_contracts	438
9 tb_sessions	765797
10 tb_results	0

The Doms Output pane displays the following message:

```

15000 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
765797 Sessions added.
3157 Non unique records found.

```

2.3 Crearea bazei de date depozit și a utilizatorilor

```

create table tbdw_trainers (id int, trainer_id int, first_name Varchar2(100), last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50), birth_date Date, hire_date Date, contract_end_date Date, gender Varchar2 (25));

```

```

create table tbdw_customers (id int, customer_id int, first_name Varchar2(100), last_name Varchar2(100), email Varchar2 (200),
phone_number Varchar2(50), date_of_birth Date, gender Varchar2(20),
has_health_issues Number(1) default 0);

```

```

create table tbdw_subscriptions_history (id int, subscription_id int, customer_subscription_id int, customer_id int, start_time_id date,
end_time_id date, price number(6));

```

```

create table tbdw_subscriptions ( id int, subscription_id int, max_number_sessions int, title varchar2 (256),
description Varchar2 (1024), with_trainer int, max_number_days int );

```

```

create table tbdw_sessions_history ( id int, session_id int, customer_id int, trainer_id int, location_id int, customer_subscription_id int,
start_time_id date );

```

```

create table tbdw_locations ( id int, location_id int, capacity int, state_name varchar2 (256), city_name varchar2 (256), address varchar2 (256),
city_id int, state_id int );

```

```

create table tbdw_time (timp_id date, an int, semestru int, trimestru int, luna int, saptamana_an int, saptamana_luna int, zi_an int,
zi_luna int, zi_saptamana int, zi_ume varchar(100), luna_ume varchar(100), weekend int, an_bisect int,
saptamana_calendar int, saptamana_an_business int);

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.128 seconds

Table TBDM_TRAINERS created.

Table TBDM_CUSTOMERS created.

Table TBDM_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY created.

Table TBDM_SUBSCRIPTIONS created.

Table TBDM_SESSIONS_HISTORY created.

Table TBDM_LOCATIONS created.

Table TBDM_TIME created.

Script Output x Query Result x

All Rows Fetched: 7 in 0.072 seconds

TABLE_NAME
1 TBDM_CUSTOMERS
2 TBDM_LOCATIONS
3 TBDM_SESSIONS_HISTORY
4 TBDM_SUBSCRIPTIONS
5 TBDM_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY
6 TBDM_TIME
7 TBDM_TRAINERS

```
alter session set "_ORACLE_SCRIPT"=true;
```

```
create user dwbi_dw identified by dwbi_dw_password password expire;
grant create session to dwbi_dw;
```

```
create profile dwbi_dw_employees limit
cpu_per_call 90000
sessions_per_user 1
password_life_time 7
failed_login_attempts 3;
```

```
alter user dwbi_dw profile dwbi_dw_employees;
```

```
select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like 'dwbi_%';
```

```
alter user dwbi_dw account unlock;
alter user dwbi_dw identified by dwbi_dw_password;
```

```
select username, authentication_type, account_status, expiry_date, created
from dba_users
order by created desc;
```

```
grant select on tbdw_customers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_trainers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_locations to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_time to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_subscriptions to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_subscriptions_history to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tbdw_sessions_history to dwbi_dw;
```

```
grant select on tb_customers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_trainers to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_results to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_contracts to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_cities to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_states to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_locations to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_sessions to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_customers_subscriptions to dwbi_dw;
grant select on tb_subscriptions to dwbi_dw;
```

```
SELECT * FROM DBA_TAB_PRIVS where lower(table_name) like 'tb_%';
```

Se creaza utilizatorul “dwbi_dw” cu parola “dwbi_dw_password” si i se da dreptul “create session”.

Se creaza profiluri de utilizatori pentru utilizatorii D.W. avand consumul de CPU per apel sa nu depaseasca 900 secunde, sa aiba dreptul la o singura sesiune la un moment dat, timpul de viata al unei parole sa fie de 30 de zile si sa poata gresi parola de maxim 3 ori.

Utilizatorul "dwbi_dw" primește drepturi de select pe toate tabelele din O.L.T.P și D.W.

2.4 Popularea cu informații a bazei de date depozit folosind ca sursă datele din baza de date OLTP

Instructiuni de autoincrementare PK pentru D.W.

```

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_trainers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_trainers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

```

```

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_customers_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_customers_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_subscriptions_history_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_subscriptions_history_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_subscriptions_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_subscriptions_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_sessions_history_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_sessions_history_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

CREATE SEQUENCE tbdw_locations_seq START WITH 1;
ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations MODIFY id int DEFAULT tbdw_locations_seq.nextval NOT NULL;

```


Transfer date tabel tbdw_trainers

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_trainers_insert AS

```

t_trainer_id tbdw_trainers.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_first_name tbdw_trainers.first_name%TYPE;
t_last_name tbdw_trainers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tbdw_trainers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tbdw_trainers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_date_of_birth tbdw_trainers.birth_date%TYPE;
t_gender tbdw_trainers.gender%TYPE;
t_hire_date tbdw_trainers.hire_date%TYPE;
t_contract_end_date tbdw_trainers.contract_end_date%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_unique_email tbdw_customers.email%TYPE;
t_unique_trainer_id tbdw_customers.customer_id%TYPE;
t_non_unique_records_found number;

BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT trainer_id into t_count_number FROM tb_trainers where rownum = 1 order by trainer_id asc;
    SELECT trainer_id into t_max_number FROM tb_trainers where rownum = 1 order by trainer_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_count_number := 0;
      t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Trainers in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

  t_trainer_id := 0;
  t_unique_email := null;
  t_unique_trainer_id := null;
  BEGIN
    select trainer_id into t_trainer_id from tb_trainers where trainer_id = l_counter;
  EXCEPTION
```

```

WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_trainer_id := 0;
END;

IF t_trainer_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
        select trainer_id,email into t_unique_trainer_id,t_unique_email from tbdw_trainers where trainer_id = t_trainer_id;
    EXCEPTION
        WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
            t_unique_email := null;
            t_unique_trainer_id := null;
        END;
    IF t_unique_trainer_id is null and t_unique_email is null THEN

        select tb1.trainer_id, tb1.first_name, tb1.last_name, tb1.email, tb1.phone_number, tb1.birth_date, tb1.gender , tb2.start_date,
        tb2.end_date
        into t_trainer_id, t_first_name, t_last_name, t_email, t_phone_number, t_date_of_birth, t_gender, t_hire_date,
        t_contract_end_date
        from tb_trainers tb1, tb_contracts tb2
        where tb1.trainer_id = tb2.trainer_id
        and tb1.trainer_id = t_trainer_id;

        INSERT INTO tbdw_trainers
        (
            trainer_id,
            first_name,
            last_name,
            email,
            phone_number,
            birth_date,
            hire_date,
            contract_end_date,
            gender
        )
        VALUES
        (
            t_trainer_id,
            t_first_name,
            t_last_name,
            t_email,
            t_phone_number,
            t_date_of_birth,
            t_hire_date,
            t_contract_end_date,
            t_gender
        );

        t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
    ELSE
        t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
    END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Trainers transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_trainers_insert;

```

end;

```
END Loop;

dms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Trainers transferred. ');
dms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');

END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_trainers_insert;
end;
```

Task completed in 0.166 seconds

Procedure **TBDW_TRAINERS_INSERT** compiled

438 Trainers in the OLTP.
438 Trainers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Doms Output

438 Trainers in the OLTP.
438 Trainers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

```
select * from tbdw_trainers order by id desc;
```

ID	TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	HIRE_DATE	CONTRACT_END_DATE	GENDER
1	438	Lydia	Bates	LydiaBates438@t.dwb1.com	1646485165	17-NOV-80	27-OCT-16	27-OCT-19	female
2	437	Ryan	Green	RyanGreen437@t.dwb1.com	3217194227	28-NOV-96	17-JUN-07	17-MAR-09	male
3	436	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes436@t.dwb1.com	5567697233	24-NOV-72	01-AUG-16	01-JAN-18	male
4	435	Hannah	Bates	HannahBates435@t.dwb1.com	3827490419	01-AUG-84	12-SEP-22	12-DEC-22	female
5	434	Julia	Palmer	JuliaPalmer434@t.dwb1.com	7103692916	21-APR-75	09-SEP-09	09-JAN-12	female
6	433	Elaine	Brooks	ElaineBrooks433@t.dwb1.com	2179821244	08-JUN-92	14-MAY-22	14-APR-28	female
7	432	Elaine	Hughes	ElaineHughes432@t.dwb1.com	3644255049	11-MAY-73	23-JUN-17	23-JUL-22	female
8	431	Louis	Holmes	LouisHolmes431@t.dwb1.com	2242239332	11-SEP-77	02-SEP-10	02-OCT-10	male
9	430	Charles	Cooper	CharlesCooper430@t.dwb1.com	8117552651	06-NOV-99	07-FEB-23	07-AUG-26	male
10	429	Vivian	Andrews	VivianAndrews429@t.dwb1.com	5305323821	07-SEP-97	19-SEP-08	19-FEB-09	female
11	428	Hannah	Rose	HannahRose428@t.dwb1.com	4549964990	15-MAR-80	09-DEC-05	09-APR-10	female
12	427	Logan	Clarke	LoganClarke427@t.dwb1.com	4445982255	29-APR-81	01-JUL-19	01-JAN-20	male
13	426	Amanda	Shepard	AmandaShepard426@t.dwb1.com	9371863563	13-AUG-95	04-OCT-02	04-DEC-03	female
14	425	Louis	Stevens	LouisStevens425@t.dwb1.com	8377578513	05-APR-80	19-DEC-15	19-SEP-19	male
15	424	Alice	Shepard	AliceShepard424@t.dwb1.com	6271273661	26-MAY-76	26-JUL-05	26-JAN-08	female
16	423	Helen	Stevens	HelenStevens423@t.dwb1.com	7799049475	06-APR-84	28-OCT-20	28-JAN-21	female
17	422	Fabian	Holmes	FabianHolmes422@t.dwb1.com	2858469512	27-JUL-99	06-SEP-15	06-MAY-20	male
18	421	Oscar	Brooks	OscarBrooks421@t.dwb1.com	9165062439	23-OCT-72	12-AUG-05	12-MAY-08	male
19	420	Elizabeth	Hopkins	ElizabethHopkins420@t.dwb1.com	9033544619	28-JAN-85	09-SEP-05	09-JAN-07	female
20	419	Amelia	Stevens	AmeliaStevens419@t.dwb1.com	8122281350	16-JUN-86	06-MAR-11	06-MAR-15	female

Transfer date tabel tbdw_customers

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_customers_insert AS

```
t_customer_id tbdw_customers.customer_id%TYPE;
t_first_name tbdw_customers.first_name%TYPE;
t_last_name tbdw_customers.last_name%TYPE;
t_email tbdw_customers.email%TYPE;
t_phone_number tbdw_customers.phone_number%TYPE;
t_date_of_birth tbdw_customers.date_of_birth%TYPE;
t_gender tbdw_customers.gender%TYPE;
t_has_health_issues tbdw_customers.has_health_issues%TYPE;
```

```

t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_unique_email tbdw_customers.email%TYPE;
t_unique_customer_id tbdw_customers.customer_id%TYPE;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT customer_id into t_count_number FROM tb_customers where rownum = 1 order by customer_id asc;
    SELECT customer_id into t_max_number FROM tb_customers where rownum = 1 order by customer_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_count_number := 0;
    t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Customers in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

  t_customer_id := 0;
  t_unique_email := null;
  t_unique_customer_id := null;

  select customer_id into t_customer_id from tb_customers where customer_id = l_counter;

  IF t_customer_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
      select customer_id,email into t_unique_customer_id,t_unique_email from tbdw_customers where customer_id = t_customer_id;
    EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_unique_email := null;
      t_unique_customer_id := null;
    END;
    IF t_unique_customer_id is null and t_unique_email is null THEN

      select customer_id,first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, date_of_birth, gender, has_health_issues
      into t_customer_id, t_first_name, t_last_name, t_email, t_phone_number, t_date_of_birth, t_gender, t_has_health_issues
      from tb_customers
      where customer_id = t_customer_id;

      INSERT INTO tbdw_customers
      (
        customer_id,
        first_name,
        last_name,
        email,
        phone_number ,
        date_of_birth,
        gender,
        has_health_issues
      )
      VALUES
      (
        t_customer_id,
        t_first_name,
        t_last_name,
        t_email,
        t_phone_number,
        t_date_of_birth,
        t_gender,
```

```

        t_has_health_issues
    );

    t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
    t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Customers transfered.');
```

```

dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

```

END;
```

```

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_customers_insert;
end;
```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window shows a PL/SQL procedure named `TBDW_CUSTOMERS_INSERT` being executed. The `Script Output` window shows the following output:

```

Procedure TBDW_CUSTOMERS_INSERT compiled
3872 Customers in the OLTP.
3872 Customers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.
```

The `Doms Output` window shows the following output:

```

438 Trainers in the OLTP.
438 Trainers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

3872 Customers in the OLTP.
3872 Customers transferred.
0 Non unique records found.
```

The `Compiler - Log` window shows the compilation details:

```

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.
```

The `Connections` window on the left shows the database structure, including tables like `TBDW_CUSTOMERS`, `TBDW_TRAINERS`, and `TBDW_HEALTH`. The `Reports` window at the bottom left shows various report categories.

Transfer date tabel *tblw_subscriptions*

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tblw_subscriptions_insert AS
```

```

t_subscription_id tblw_subscriptions.subscription_id%TYPE;
t_max_number_sessions tblw_subscriptions.max_number_sessions%TYPE;
t_max_number_days tblw_subscriptions.max_number_days%TYPE;
t_title tblw_subscriptions.title%TYPE;
t_description tblw_subscriptions.description%TYPE;
t_with_trainer tblw_subscriptions.with_trainer%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_subscription_id tblw_subscriptions.subscription_id%TYPE;

```

```
BEGIN
```

```
  BEGIN
```

```
    SELECT subscription_id into t_count_number FROM tbl_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by subscription_id asc;
```

```
    SELECT subscription_id into t_max_number FROM tbl_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by subscription_id desc;
```

```
  EXCEPTION
```

```
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
```

```
    t_count_number := 0;
```

```
    t_max_number := 0;
```

```
  END;
```

```
  t_transfers := 0;
```

```
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
```

```
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Subscriptions in the OLTP.');
```

```
  for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
```

```
  Loop
```

```
    t_subscription_id := 0;
```

```
  BEGIN
```

```
    select subscription_id into t_subscription_id from tbl_subscriptions where subscription_id = l_counter;
```

```
  EXCEPTION
```

```
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
```

```
    t_subscription_id := 0;
```

```

END;

IF t_subscription_id > 0 THEN

BEGIN
    select subscription_id into t_unique_subscription_id from tbdw_subscriptions where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;
EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
        t_unique_subscription_id := null;
END;

IF t_unique_subscription_id is null THEN

    select subscription_id, max_number_sessions, sb_title, sb_description, with_trainer, max_number_days
    into t_subscription_id, t_max_number_sessions, t_title, t_description, t_with_trainer, t_max_number_days
    from tb_subscriptions
    where subscription_id = t_subscription_id;

    INSERT INTO tbdw_subscriptions
    (
        subscription_id,
        max_number_sessions,
        title,
        description,
        with_trainer,
        max_number_days
    )
    VALUES
    (
        t_subscription_id,
        t_max_number_sessions,
        t_title,
        t_description,
        t_with_trainer,
        t_max_number_sessions
    );

    t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
    t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Subscriptions transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_subscriptions_insert;
end;

```

```

END Loop;
dms_output.put_line ('t_transfers || ' Subscriptions transferred.');
```

```

dms_output.put_line ('t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_subscriptions_insert;
end;

Task completed in 0.064 seconds

Procedure **TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_INSERT** compiled

20 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
20 Subscriptions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Dims Output | Buffer Size: 20000

dms_output

0 Non unique records found.
20 Subscriptions in the OLTP.
20 Subscriptions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

```

select * from tbdw_subscriptions order by id desc;
```

Query Result | Script Output | Query Result 1

All Rows Fetched: 20 in 0.005 seconds

ID	SUBSCRIPTIONS	MAX_NUMBER_SESSIONS	TITLE	DESCRIPTION
1	20	20	16 Pachet 2 luni fitness cu antrenor	Oferta include 16 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 60 de z...
2	19	19	12 Pachet lunar fitness cu antrenor	Oferta include 12 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 31 de z...
3	18	18	8 Pachet lunar fitness cu antrenor	Oferta include 8 intrari la programul de fitness ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 31 de zi...
4	17	17	11 Intrare Sala Fitness cu Antrenor	Oferta include acces la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea pentru a ant...
5	16	16	365 Abonament anual aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 1 an la programul de aerobic
6	15	15	180 Abonament demi aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 6 luni la programul de aerobic
7	14	14	90 Abonament quarter aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 3 luni la programul de aerobic
8	13	13	31 Abonament lunar sedinte aerobic	Acces zilnic timp de 1 luna la programul de aerobic
9	12	12	365 Abonament anual piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 1 an la piscina
10	11	11	180 Abonament demi piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 6 luni la piscina
11	10	10	90 Abonament quarter piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 3 luni la piscina
12	9	9	31 Abonament lunar piscina	Acces zilnic timp de 31 de zile la piscina
13	8	8	365 Abonament anual fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 1 an la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea pentru a...
14	7	7	180 Abonament demi fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 6 luni de zile la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greuta...
15	6	6	90 Abonament quarter fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 3 luni de zile la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greuta...
16	5	5	31 Abonament lunar fitness	Acces zilnic timp de 31 de zile la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea p...
17	4	4	8 Abonament lunar sedinte aerobic	Oferta include 8 intrari la programul de aerobic ce pot fi utilizate intr-un interval de 31 de zi...
18	3	3	11 Intrare Sala Fitness	Oferta include acces la aparate pentru antrenament cardio dar si aparate cu greutatea pentru a ant...
19	2	2	11 Intrare piscina copii	Oferta valabila pentru copii cu varstele cuprinse intre 10-16 ani

Dims Output | Buffer Size: 20000

Messages - Log

Transfer date tabel tbdw_locations

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_locations_insert AS

```

t_location_id tbdw_locations.location_id%TYPE;
t_capacity tbdw_locations.capacity%TYPE;
t_state_name tbdw_locations.state_name%TYPE;
t_city_name tbdw_locations.city_name%TYPE;
t_address tbdw_locations.address%TYPE;
t_city_id tbdw_locations.city_id%TYPE;
t_state_id tbdw_locations.state_id%TYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_location_id tbdw_locations.location_id%TYPE;
```

```

BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT location_id into t_count_number FROM tb_locations where rownum = 1 order by location_id asc;
    SELECT location_id into t_max_number FROM tb_locations where rownum = 1 order by location_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_count_number := 0;
    t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Locations in the OLTP.');
```

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
Loop

```

  t_location_id := 0;

  BEGIN
    select location_id into t_location_id from tb_locations where location_id = l_counter;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_location_id := 0;
  END;

  IF t_location_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
      select location_id into t_unique_location_id from tbdw_locations where location_id = t_location_id;
    EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_unique_location_id := null;
    END;
    IF t_unique_location_id is null THEN

      select tb1.location_id, tb1.location_capacity, tb3.state_name, tb2.city_name, tb1.address, tb1.city_id, tb2.state_id
      into t_location_id, t_capacity, t_state_name, t_city_name, t_address, t_city_id, t_state_id
      from tb_locations tb1, tb_cities tb2, tb_states tb3
      where tb1.location_id = t_location_id and tb1.city_id = tb2.city_id and tb2.state_id = tb3.state_id;

      INSERT INTO tbdw_locations
      (
        location_id,
        capacity,
        state_name,
        city_name,
        address,
        city_id,
        state_id
      )
      VALUES
      (
        t_location_id,
        t_capacity,
        t_state_name,
        t_city_name,
        t_address,
        t_city_id,
        t_state_id
      );

      t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
    ELSE
      t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
    
```

```
END IF;
```

```
END IF;
```

```
END Loop;
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Locations transferred.');
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

```
END;
```

```
set serveroutput on;
```

```
begin
```

```
tbdw_locations_insert;
```

```
end;
```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer environment. The main window shows a PL/SQL script with the following code:

```
END Loop;  
  
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Locations transferred.');
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found.');
```

```
END;
```

```
set serveroutput on;
```

```
begin
```

```
tbdw_locations_insert;
```

```
end;
```

The Script Output window shows the execution results:

```
Task completed in 0.077 seconds  
  
Procedure TBOW_LOCATIONS_INSERT compiled  
  
70 Locations in the OLTP.  
70 Locations transferred.  
0 Non unique records found.  
  
PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.
```

The Dims Output window shows the output of the procedure:

```
0 Non unique records found.  
70 Locations in the OLTP.  
70 Locations transferred.  
0 Non unique records found.
```

The Connections pane on the left shows the database schema structure, including tables like TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TBOW_CUSTOMERS, TBOW_LOCATIONS, TBOW_SESSIONS_HISTORY, TBOW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY, TBOW_TIME, TBOW_TRAINERS, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, TBE_LAST_NAMES, and TRANSACTION_BACKOUT_REPORTS.

Transfer date tabel tblw_time

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tblw_time_insert AS

```
t_max_date date;
t_min_date date;
l_counter date;
l_variable_interval varchar(2);
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_timp_id tblw_time.timp_id%TYPE;
```

BEGIN

```
SELECT to_date('01-JAN-1964') into t_min_date FROM dual;
SELECT to_date('31-DEC-1964') + interval '24' hour into t_max_date FROM dual;
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (to_char(t_min_date,'YYYY-MON-DD HH24:MI') || ' Is the start date.');
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (to_char(t_max_date,'YYYY-MON-DD HH24:MI') || ' Is the end date.');
```

```
t_transfers := 0;
t_non_unique_records_found :=0;
l_counter := t_min_date;
```

BEGIN

```
while l_counter <= t_max_date
LOOP
```

```
l_variable_interval := to_char(l_counter,'HH24');
--dbms_output.put_line (to_char(l_counter,'YYYY-MON-DD HH24:MI') || ' Is the current date in loop. and ' || cast(l_variable_interval as integer) || ' is current hour');
```

BEGIN

```
select timp_id into t_unique_timp_id from tblw_time where timp_id = l_counter and rownum = 1;
```

EXCEPTION

```
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
```

```
t_unique_timp_id := to_date('01-JAN-1100');
```

END;

```
IF t_unique_timp_id = to_date('01-JAN-1100') then
```

```

insert into tbdw_time
select
  data timp_id,
  extract(year from data) an,
  case when extract(month from data) < 7 then 1 else 2 end semestru,
  TO_CHAR(data, 'q') trimestru,
  extract(month from data) luna,
  to_char(data,'WW') SAPTAMANA_AN,
  to_char(data,'W')SAPTAMANA_LUNA,
  to_char(data,'DDD') ZI_AN,
  to_char(data,'DD') ZI_LUNA,
  to_char(data,'D') ZI_SAPTAMANA,
  to_char(data,'DAY') ZI_NUME,
  to_char(data,'MONTH') LUNA_NUME,
  case when to_char(data,'D') not in (1,7) then 0 else 1 end WEEKEND,
  case when mod(extract(year from data), 4) = 0 and mod(extract(year from data), 4) <> 100 then 1 else 0 end AN_BISECT,
  to_number(to_char(data,'IW')) SAPTAMANA_CALENDAR,
  case when to_number(to_char(data,'D')) <> 1 then to_number(to_char(data,'IW')) - 1
    else to_number(to_char(data,'IW')) end SAPTAMANA_AN_BUSINESS
from(
  select to_date(l_counter) + cast(l_variable_interval as integer)/24 as data from dual);

  t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
  t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

  l_counter := l_counter + interval '1' hour;
END Loop;
END;
dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Records transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');

END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_time_insert;
end;

```


Datele introduse in tabelul "Time" au fost generate ruland procedura pentru intervale de 10 ani de zile. Pentru fiecare zi din an, procedura va introduce 24 de intrari, pentru cele 24 de ore din zi. Data si ora sunt stocate in variabila "timp_id".

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query result table with the following columns: TO_CHAR(TIMP_ID,YYYY-MM-DDHH24-MI), AN, SEMESTRU, TRIMESTRU, LLUNA, SAPTAMANA_AN, SAPTAMANA_LLUNA, ZI_AN, ZI_LLUNA, ZI_SAPTAMANA, LLUNA_NUME, WEEKEND, AN_BISECT, and SAPTA. The table contains 19 rows of data, starting with a timestamp of 2025-01-01 00:00 and ending with 2024-12-31 06:00. The data shows a repeating pattern of subscription periods.

TO_CHAR(TIMP_ID,YYYY-MM-DDHH24-MI)	AN	SEMESTRU	TRIMESTRU	LLUNA	SAPTAMANA_AN	SAPTAMANA_LLUNA	ZI_AN	ZI_LLUNA	ZI_SAPTAMANA	LLUNA_NUME	WEEKEND	AN_BISECT	SAPTA
1 2025-01-01 00:00	2025	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4 WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	0
2 2024-12-31 23:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
3 2024-12-31 22:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
4 2024-12-31 21:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
5 2024-12-31 20:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
6 2024-12-31 19:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
7 2024-12-31 18:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
8 2024-12-31 17:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
9 2024-12-31 16:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
10 2024-12-31 15:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
11 2024-12-31 14:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
12 2024-12-31 13:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
13 2024-12-31 12:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
14 2024-12-31 11:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
15 2024-12-31 10:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
16 2024-12-31 09:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
17 2024-12-31 08:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
18 2024-12-31 07:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1
19 2024-12-31 06:00	2024	2	4	12	53	5	366	31	3	TUESDAY	DECEMBER	0	1

Transfer date tabel *tbdw_subscriptions_history*

CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE *tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert AS*

```
t_subscription_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.subscription_idTYPE;
t_customer_subscription_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.customer_subscription_idTYPE;
t_customer_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.customer_idTYPE;
t_start_time_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.start_time_idTYPE;
t_end_time_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.end_time_idTYPE;
t_price tbdw_subscriptions_history.priceTYPE;
t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_customer_subscription_id tbdw_subscriptions_history.customer_subscription_idTYPE;
```

BEGIN

BEGIN

```
SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_count_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by
customer_subscription_id asc;
```

```
SELECT customer_subscription_id into t_max_number FROM tb_customers_subscriptions where rownum = 1 order by
customer_subscription_id desc;
```

EXCEPTION

WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN

```
t_count_number := 0;
```

```
t_max_number := 0;
```

END;

```
t_transfers := 0;
```

```
t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
```

```
dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Locations in the OLTP.');
```

```
for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number
```

```
Loop
```

```
t_customer_subscription_id := 0;
```

BEGIN

```

select customer_subscription_id into t_customer_subscription_id from tb_customers_subscriptions where customer_subscription_id =
l_counter;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_customer_subscription_id := 0;
END;

IF t_customer_subscription_id > 0 THEN

BEGIN
select customer_subscription_id into t_unique_customer_subscription_id from tbdw_subscriptions_history where
customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;
EXCEPTION
WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
t_unique_customer_subscription_id := null;
END;

IF t_unique_customer_subscription_id is null THEN

select subscription_id, customer_id, start_date, end_date, price
into t_subscription_id, t_customer_id, t_start_time_id, t_end_time_id, t_price
from tb_customers_subscriptions
where customer_subscription_id = t_customer_subscription_id;

INSERT INTO tbdw_subscriptions_history
(
subscription_id,
customer_subscription_id,
customer_id,
start_time_id,
end_time_id,
price
)
VALUES
(
t_subscription_id,
t_customer_subscription_id,
t_customer_id,
t_start_time_id,
t_end_time_id,
t_price
);

t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Subscriptions transfered. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert;
end;

```

Procedure `TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_INSERT` compiled

15000 Locations in the OLTP.
15000 Subscriptions transferred.
0 Non unique records found.

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Dms Output

0 Non unique records found.
70 Locations in the OLTP.
70 Locations transferred.
0 Non unique records found.
1964-JAN-01 00:00 Is the start date.

select * from tbw_subscriptions_history order by id desc;

ID	SUBSCRIPTION_ID	CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID	CUSTOMER_ID	START_TIME_ID	END_TIME_ID	PRICE
1	15000	15	15000	1021 23-SEP-02	21-MAR-03	1245
2	14959	5	14959	1013 30-JUL-16	29-AUG-16	230
3	14998	18	14998	1039 13-JUL-04	12-AUG-04	520
4	14997	17	14997	591 01-DEC-05	01-DEC-05	70
5	14996	12	14996	2409 10-SEP-19	08-SEP-20	2040
6	14995	14	14995	178 21-MAR-16	18-JUN-16	685
7	14994	12	14994	1696 17-FEB-07	16-FEB-08	2040
8	14993	18	14993	3318 23-SEP-13	23-OCT-13	520
9	14992	14	14992	1262 11-NOV-11	05-FEB-12	685
10	14991	18	14991	600 04-DEC-22	03-JAN-23	520
11	14990	10	14990	1506 24-JUL-00	21-OCT-00	670
12	14989	9	14989	2457 14-DEC-13	13-JAN-14	300
13	14988	19	14988	118 13-JUL-22	12-AUG-22	720
14	14987	17	14987	2361 18-DEC-06	18-DEC-06	70
15	14986	17	14986	212 30-JUN-17	30-JUN-17	70
16	14985	7	14985	3422 07-OCT-19	03-APR-20	960
17	14984	5	14984	3719 17-APR-18	17-MAY-18	230
18	14983	1	14983	3316 26-JUL-15	26-JUL-15	60
19	14982	2	14982	525 09-NOV-20	09-NOV-20	30
20	14981	14	14981	2333 10-NOV-13	08-DEC-13	205

Transfer date tabel `tbw_sessions_history`

CREATE or **REPLACE PROCEDURE** `tbw_sessions_history_insert` AS

```

t_session_id tbw_sessions_history.session_id%TYPE;
t_customer_id tbw_sessions_history.customer_id%TYPE;
t_trainer_id tbw_sessions_history.trainer_id%TYPE;
t_location_id tbw_sessions_history.location_id%TYPE;
t_customer_subscription_id tbw_sessions_history.customer_subscription_id%TYPE;
t_start_time tbw_sessions_history.start_time_id%TYPE;

```

```

t_max_number number;
t_count_number number;
t_transfers number;
t_non_unique_records_found number;
t_unique_session_id tbdw_sessions_history.session_id%TYPE;
BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT session_id into t_count_number FROM tb_sessions where rownum = 1 order by session_id asc;
    SELECT session_id into t_max_number FROM tb_sessions where rownum = 1 order by session_id desc;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_count_number := 0;
    t_max_number := 0;
  END;

  t_transfers := 0;
  t_non_unique_records_found := 0;
  dbms_output.put_line (t_max_number || ' Records in the OLTP.');
```

-- t_count_number := 800001;

-- t_max_number := 900000;

for l_counter in t_count_number..t_max_number

Loop

```

  BEGIN
    select session_id into t_session_id from tb_sessions where session_id = l_counter;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    t_session_id := 0;
  END;

  IF t_session_id > 0 THEN

    BEGIN
      select session_id into t_unique_session_id from tbdw_sessions_history where session_id = t_session_id;
    EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      t_unique_session_id := null;
    END;

    IF t_unique_session_id is null THEN

      select customer_id, customer_subscription_id, location_id, trainer_id, start_date
      into t_customer_id, t_customer_subscription_id, t_location_id, t_trainer_id, t_start_time
      from tb_sessions
      where session_id = t_session_id;

      INSERT INTO tbdw_sessions_history
      (
        session_id,
        customer_id,
        trainer_id,
        location_id,
        customer_subscription_id,
        start_time_id
      )
      VALUES
      (
        t_session_id,
        t_customer_id,
        t_trainer_id,
        t_location_id,
        t_customer_subscription_id,
        t_start_time

```

```

);

t_transfers := t_transfers + 1;
ELSE
t_non_unique_records_found := t_non_unique_records_found + 1;
END IF;

END IF;

END Loop;

dbms_output.put_line (t_transfers || ' Sessions transferred. ');
dbms_output.put_line (t_non_unique_records_found || ' Non unique records found. ');
END;
/

set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_sessions_history_insert;
end;

```


Afisare count(*) in tabellele din DW

```

select 'tbdw_trainers' Table_name, count(*) "COUNT" from tbdw_trainers
union all
select 'tbdw_customers', count(*) from tbdw_customers
union all
select 'tbdw_subscriptions', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions
union all
select 'tbdw_locatons', count(*) from tbdw_locatons
union all
select 'tbdw_time', count(*) from tbdw_time
union all
select 'tbdw_subscriptions_history', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions_history
union all

```

```
select 'tbdw_sessions_history', count(*) from tbdw_sessions_history;
```

The screenshot shows a database management tool interface. The main window displays a SQL query in the Query Builder:

```
union all  
select 'tbdw_customers', count(*) from tbdw_customers  
union all  
select 'tbdw_subscriptions', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions  
union all  
select 'tbdw_locations', count(*) from tbdw_locations  
union all  
select 'tbdw_time', count(*) from tbdw_time  
union all  
select 'tbdw_subscriptions_history', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions_history  
union all  
select 'tbdw_sessions_history', count(*) from tbdw_sessions_history;
```

The Query Result pane shows the following data:

TABLE_NAME	COUNT
1 tbdw_trainers	438
2 tbdw_customers	3872
3 tbdw_subscriptions	20
4 tbdw_locations	70
5 tbdw_time	534745
6 tbdw_subscriptions_history	15000
7 tbdw_sessions_history	765797

The Dims Output pane shows the following information:

```
0 Non unique records found.  
765797 Records in the OLTP.  
100000 Sessions transferred.  
0 Non unique records found.  
765797 Records in the OLTP.
```

2.5 Definirea constrângerilor

Constrangerile Primary Key pentru OLTP:

```
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (trainer_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (customer_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_results ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_results_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (result_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (customer_subscription_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (subscription_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (session_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_locations_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (location_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_contracts ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_contracts_pk PRIMARY KEY (contract_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_states ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_states_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (state_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_cities ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_cities_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (city_id));
```


Constrangerile Foreign Key pentru OLTP:

```
ALTER TABLE tb_results ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_results_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id) REFERENCES tb_customers(customer_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_subscriptions_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id) REFERENCES tb_customers(customer_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_customers_subscriptions_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (subscription_id) REFERENCES tb_subscriptions(subscription_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_customer_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_subscription_id) REFERENCES tb_customers_subscriptions(customer_subscription_id);
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_traier_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (trainer_id) REFERENCES tb_trainers(trainer_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tb_customers(customer_id));
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_sessions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_sessions_location_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (location_id) REFERENCES tb_locations(location_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_locations_city_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (city_id) REFERENCES tb_cities(city_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_contracts ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_contracts_trainer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (trainer_id) REFERENCES tb_trainers(trainer_id) );
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_cities ADD ( CONSTRAINT tb_cities_state_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (state_id) REFERENCES tb_states(state_id) );
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query execution window with the following output:

```
Table TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS altered.
Table TB_SESSIONS altered.
Table TB_SESSIONS altered.
Table TB_SESSIONS altered.
Table TB_LOCATIONS altered.
Table TB_CONTRACTS altered.
Table TB_CITIES altered.
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a query execution window with the following output:

```
CONSTRAINT_NAME      CONSTRAINT_TYPE  TABLE_NAME      R_CONSTRAINT_NAME  STATUS
1 TB_CITIES_STATE_ID_FK      R              TB_CITIES        TB_STATES_ID_FK    ENABLED
2 TB_CONTRACTS_TRAINER_ID_FK  R              TB_CONTRACTS    TB_TRAINERS_ID_FK  ENABLED
3 TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_SUBSCRIPTION_ID_FK R              TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_FK  ENABLED
4 TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_CUSTOMER_ID_FK  R              TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS TB_CUSTOMERS_ID_FK  ENABLED
5 TB_LOCATIONS_CITY_ID_FK    R              TB_LOCATIONS    TB_CITIES_ID_FK    ENABLED
6 TB_RESULTS_CUSTOMER_ID_FK  R              TB_RESULTS      TB_CUSTOMERS_ID_FK  ENABLED
7 TB_SESSIONS_LOCATION_ID_FK R              TB_SESSIONS     TB_LOCATIONS_ID_FK  ENABLED
8 TB_SESSIONS_CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID_FK  R              TB_SESSIONS     TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_FK  ENABLED
9 TB_SESSIONS_TRAILER_ID_FK  R              TB_SESSIONS     TB_TRAINERS_ID_FK  ENABLED
```

Constragerile UNIQUE pentru OLTP:

```
ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
```

```
ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
```

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing a project named 'dvbi_project' with various database objects like TTSQ\$, TTS_ERROR\$, TYPE_MISC\$, etc.
- Worksheet:** The main editor contains the following SQL script:

```
27 AND cons.owner = 'SYS'  
28 AND cons.table_name like 'TB%'  
29 ORDER BY cols.table_name, cols.position;  
30  
31 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);  
32  
33 ALTER TABLE tb_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);  
34  
35
```
- Script Output:** The output pane shows the execution results:

```
Table TB_SESSIONS altered.  
Table TB_LOCATIONS altered.  
Table TB_CONTRACTS altered.  
Table TB_STATES altered.  
Table TB_CITIES altered.  
Table TB_TRAINERS altered.  
Table TB_CUSTOMERS altered.
```
- Script Output:** Below the main output, it indicates 'Task completed in 0.089 seconds'.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Worksheet:** The main editor contains the following SQL query:

```
23 select cons.constraint_name, cons.constraint_type, cons.table_name, cons.status  
24 from all_constraints cons, all_cons_columns cols  
25 where cons.constraint_type = 'U'  
26 AND cons.constraint_name = cols.constraint_name  
27 AND cons.owner = 'SYS'  
28 AND cons.table_name like 'TB%'  
29 ORDER BY cons.table_name, cols.position;  
30  
31 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tb_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
```
- Script Output:** The output pane shows the query results:

```
All Rows Fetched: 2 in 0.251 seconds  
+-----+-----+-----+-----+  
| CONSTRAINT_NAME | CONSTRAINT_TYPE | TABLE_NAME | STATUS |  
+-----+-----+-----+-----+  
| TB_CUSTOMERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL | U | TB_CUSTOMERS | ENABLED |  
| TB_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL | U | TB_TRAINERS | ENABLED |  
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
```
- Script Output:** Below the main output, it indicates 'All Rows Fetched: 2 in 0.251 seconds'.

Click on an identifier with the Control key down to perform "Go to Declaration"

| Line: 29 Column: 41 | Insert | Modified | Window: O

Constrangerile Primary Key pentru DW

```
ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_trainers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_customers_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_locations_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_time ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (time_id));
```

The screenshot displays the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing a project named 'dwb_project' with various schema objects like TSQS, TTS_ERRORS, TYPE_MISC, etc.
- Worksheet:** The main area contains a 'Query Builder' window with the following SQL script:

```
220 ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
221  
222 ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
223  
224 ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_locations_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (id));  
225  
226 ALTER TABLE tbdw_time ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_id_pk PRIMARY KEY (time_id));  
227  
228
```
- Script Output:** Below the worksheet, a 'Script Output' window shows the results of the execution:

```
Task completed in 0.195 seconds  
Table TBW_TRAINERS altered.  
Table TBW_CUSTOMERS altered.  
Table TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY altered.  
Table TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS altered.  
Table TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY altered.  
Table TBW_LOCATIONS altered.  
Table TBW_TIME altered.
```
- Reports:** A 'Reports' window on the left lists various report types like 'Analytic View Reports', 'Data Dictionary Reports', etc.
- Bottom Panel:** A 'Doms Output' window at the bottom shows the connection name 'dwb_project' and a buffer size of 20000.

Costrangerile Foreign Key pentru DW

```

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_customers(customer_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_trainer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (trainer_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_trainers(trainer_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_location_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (location_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_locations(location_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD ( CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_customer_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY
(customer_subscription_id) REFERENCES tbdw_subscriptions_history(customer_subscription_id)) ;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD (CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_subscription_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (subscription_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_subscriptions(subscription_id));

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD (CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_customer_id_fk FOREIGN KEY (customer_id)
REFERENCES tbdw_customers(customer_id));
  
```



```
ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_unique_session_id UNIQUE (session_id) disable validate;  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_unique_subscription_id UNIQUE (subscription_id) disable validate;  
ALTER TABLE tbdw_time modify CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_id_pk disable validate;
```


Pentru fiecare tabel, tbdw_trainers, tbdw_customers, tbdw_locations, tbdw_subscriptions, tbdw_subscriptions_history, tbdw_sessions_history am definit cate o constrangere de tip UNIQUE avand proprietatile "disable validate". Dupa ce aceste constrangeri au fost implementate, operatiile de tip, insert, update si delete pe aceste tabele nu vor putea fi executate.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays the following SQL commands:

```

select constraint_name, constraint_type, status, validated, index_name
from user_constraints
where lower(table_name) like 'tbdw_%'
and lower(constraint_type) like 'u';

ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_trainers_unique_trainer_id UNIQUE (trainer_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_customers_unique_customer_id UNIQUE (customer_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_locations_unique_location_id UNIQUE (location_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id UNIQUE (customer_subscription_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_unique_session_id UNIQUE (session_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_unique_subscription_id UNIQUE (subscription_id) disable validate;

```

The Query Result window shows the following table:

CONSTRAINT_NAME	CONSTRAINT_TYPE	STATUS	VALIDATED	INDEX_NAME
TBDW_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL	U	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL
TBDW_CUSTOMERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL	U	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_CUSTOMERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL
TBDW_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_TRAINER_ID	U	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)
TBDW_CUSTOMERS_UNIQUE_CUSTOMER_ID	U	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)
TBDW_LOCATIONS_UNIQUE_LOCATION_ID	U	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)
TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_UNIQUE_CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID	U	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)
TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY_UNIQUE_SESSION_ID	U	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)
TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_UNIQUE_SUBSCRIPTION_ID	U	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)

Deasemenea, pentru tabelul `tbdw_time`, cheia primara "timp_id" a fost modificata si i s-au atribuit proprietatile "disable validate" astfel incat cele 3 operatii nu vor putea fi executate nici pe acesta.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays the following SQL commands:

```

select constraint_name, constraint_type, status, validated, index_name
from user_constraints
where lower(table_name) like 'tbdw_%'
and lower(constraint_type) like 'p';

ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_trainers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
ALTER TABLE tbdw_trainers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_trainers_unique_trainer_id UNIQUE (trainer_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_customers_unique_email UNIQUE (email);
ALTER TABLE tbdw_customers ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_customers_unique_customer_id UNIQUE (customer_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_locations ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_locations_unique_location_id UNIQUE (location_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions_history ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id UNIQUE (customer_subscription_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_sessions_history ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_sessions_history_unique_session_id UNIQUE (session_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_subscriptions ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_subscriptions_unique_subscription_id UNIQUE (subscription_id) disable validate;

ALTER TABLE tbdw_time ADD CONSTRAINT tbdw_time_pk PRIMARY KEY (timp_id) disable validate;

```

The Query Result window shows the following table:

CONSTRAINT_NAME	CONSTRAINT_TYPE	STATUS	VALIDATED	INDEX_NAME
TBDW_CUSTOMERS_ID_PK	P	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_CUSTOMERS_ID_PK
TBDW_TRAINERS_ID_PK	P	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_TRAINERS_ID_PK
TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_ID_PK	P	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_ID_PK
TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_PK	P	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_ID_PK
TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY_ID_PK	P	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY_ID_PK
TBDW_LOCATIONS_ID_PK	P	ENABLED	VALIDATED	TBDW_LOCATIONS_ID_PK
TBDW_TIME_ID_PK	P	DISABLED	VALIDATED	(null)

Pentru a adauga noi date in Data Warehouse, vom modifica constrangerea tabelului pe care dorim sa il actualizam atribuindu-i proprietatea "enable". Aplicam aceste modificari pentru tabelul de fapte "tbdw_subscriptions_history".

```
alter table tbdw_subscriptions_history modify constraint tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id enable;
```


Am adaugat 100 de intrari noi in baza de date OLTP pentru tabelul tb_customers_subscriptions. Acum acesta contine 15.100 de inregistrari, iar tabelul tb_subscriptions_history contine 15.000 de inregistrari.

```
select 'tb_customers_subscriptions' Table_name, count(*) "COUNT" from tb_customers_subscriptions
union all
select 'tbdw_subscriptions_history', count(*) from tbdw_subscriptions_history;
```


Rulam procedura de transfer de date "tbdw_subscriptions_history_insert" si observam ca cele 100 de inregistrari noi au fost transferate de la O.L.T.P la D.W.

Dupa actualizare cele doua baze de date au acelasi numar de inregistrari, ambele 15100.

Pentru a bloca din nou tabelul `tbdw_subscriptions_history` vom modifica constrangerea “`tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id`” si ii vom reatribui proprietatile “`disable validate`”

```
alter table tbdw_subscriptions_history modify constraint tbdw_subscriptions_history_unique_customer_subscription_id disable validate;
```


Vom incerca sa stergem date din acest tabel si anume inregistrarea cu id-ul 15100.

Confirmam ca aceasta intrare exista.

```
select * from tbdw_subscriptions_history where id = 15100;
```


Si executam stergerea acesteia.

Observam ca stergerea datelor nu s-a executat si am primit mesajul de eroare “ORA-25128 No insert/update/delete on table with constraint (SYS.TBDW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY_UNIQUE_CUSTOMER_SUBSCRIPTION_ID) disabled and validated”.

2.6 Definirea indecșilor și a cererilor SQL însoțite de planul de execuție al acestora (din care să reiasă ca optimizorul utilizează eficient indecșii definiți)

2.6.1 Index de tip BITMAP

Vom folosi un index de tip BITMAP pentru a determina procentajul numarului de clienti care au problem de sanatate. Vom analiza si compararea costurile unei astfel de interogari cu si fara utilizarea index-ului de tip Bitmap.

Intai analizam costurile fara utilizarea index-ului.

```
create table tbdw_customers_temp as select * from tbdw_customers;
```

```
Analyze table tbdw_customers_temp compute statistics;
```

```
select max_number_customers,
       round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as
percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
      from tbdw_customers_temp
      where has_health_issues = 1);
```


Observam costul total al acestei interogari ca fiind "28".

Se creaza un index de tip **BITMAP**

```
alter table tbdw_customers_temp add constraint tbdw_customers_temp_pk Primary Key (id) enable novalidate;
```

```
CREATE BITMAP INDEX ind_bmp_tbdw_customers_has_health_issues_test_temp
ON tbdw_customers_temp(has_health_issues);
```

```
ANALYZE INDEX ind_bmp_tbdw_customers_has_health_issues_test_temp COMPUTE STATISTICS;
```

explain plan

```
set statement_id = 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp'
```

for

```
select max_number_customers,
       round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as
percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
      from tbdw_customers_temp
      where has_health_issues = 1);
```

```
SELECT plan_table_output
```

```
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp','serial'));
```

Worksheet Query Builder

```

where has_health_issues = 1);

explain plan
set statement_id = 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp'
for
select max_number_customers,
       round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
      from tbdw_customers_temp
      where has_health_issues = 1);

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp','serial'));

```

Script Output x | Explain Plan x | Query Result x

Task completed in 0.055 seconds

INDEX IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP created.

Index IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP analyzed.

Explained.

Dims Output | Buffer Size:20000

Messages - Log

Messages | Statements

Worksheet Query Builder

```

round(max_number_customers / (select count(*) from tbdw_customers_temp) * 100,2) as percentage
from (select count(*) max_number_customers
      from tbdw_customers_temp
      where has_health_issues = 1);

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 's1_tbdw_customers_bmp_temp','serial'));

```

Script Output x | Explain Plan x | Query Result x

All Rows Fetched: 19 in 0.068 seconds

PLAN_TABLE_OUTPUT

```

1 Plan hash value: 4120872880
2
3
4 Id | Operation | Name | Rows | Bytes | Cost (%CPU) | Time |
5
6 0 | SELECT STATEMENT | | 1 | 13 | 2 (0) | 00:00:01 |
7 1 | SORT AGGREGATE | | 1 | 1 | | | |
8 2 | BITMAP CONVERSION TO ROWIDS | | 3872 | | 1 (0) | 00:00:01 |
9 3 | BITMAP INDEX FAST FULL SCAN | IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP | | | | | |
10 4 | VIEW | | 1 | 13 | 1 (0) | 00:00:01 |
11 5 | SORT AGGREGATE | | 1 | 2 | | | |
12 6 | BITMAP CONVERSION COUNT | | 1936 | 3872 | 1 (0) | 00:00:01 |
13 7 | BITMAP INDEX FAST FULL SCAN | IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP | | | | | |
14
15
16 Predicate Information (identified by operation id):
17
18
19 7 - filter("HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES"=1)

```

Dims Output | Buffer Size:20000

Messages - Log

Messages | Statements

Plan hash value: 4120872880

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		1	13	2 (0)	00:00:01
1	SORT AGGREGATE		1			
2	BITMAP CONVERSION TO ROWIDS		3872		1 (0)	00:00:01
3	BITMAP INDEX FAST FULL SCAN	IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP				
4	VIEW		1	13	1 (0)	00:00:01
5	SORT AGGREGATE		1	2		
6	BITMAP CONVERSION COUNT		1936	3872	1 (0)	00:00:01
* 7	BITMAP INDEX FAST FULL SCAN	IND_BMP_TBDW_CUSTOMERS_HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES_TEST_TEMP				

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

7 - filter("HAS_HEALTH_ISSUES"=1)

Dupa utilizarea index-ului de tip BITMAP, observam costul total al acestei interogari devenind “13”.

2.7 Definirea obiectelor de tip dimensiune, validarea acestora (din care să reiasă că datele respectă constrângerile impuse prin aceste tipuri de obiecte)

2.7.1 Obiectul dimensiune pentru tabelul “LOCATIONS”

```
CREATE DIMENSION tbdw_dim_locations
LEVEL locatie IS (tbdw_locations.id)
LEVEL oras IS (tbdw_locations.city_name)
LEVEL judet IS (tbdw_locations.state_name)
HIERARCHY h1
(
  locatie CHILD OF
  oras CHILD OF
  judet)
ATTRIBUTE locatie DETERMINES (tbdw_locations.address, tbdw_locations.capacity);
```


Se executa validarea obiectului dimensiune pentru tabelul “Locations”

```
execute dbms_dimension.validate_dimension(upper('tbw_dim_locatons'),false,true,'st_tbdw_dim_locatons');
```


Se verifica daca datele din tabelul "Locations" indeplinesc constrangerile impuse de obiectul dimensiune definit.

```
SELECT * FROM dimension_exceptions WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_locatons';
```



```
SELECT * FROM tbdw_locatons  
WHERE rowid IN (SELECT bad_rowid  
FROM dimension_exceptions  
WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_locatons');
```


In urma verificarilor se observa ca datele introduse indeplinesc constrangerile impuse de obiectul dimensiune.

2.7.2 Obiectul dimensiune pentru tabelul "TIME".

CREATE DIMENSION tbdw_dim_time

LEVEL zi IS (tbdw_time.timp_id)
 LEVEL saptamana IS (tbdw_time.saptamana_luna)
 LEVEL luna IS (tbdw_time.luna)
 LEVEL trimestru IS (tbdw_time.trimestru)
 LEVEL semestru IS (tbdw_time.semestru)
 LEVEL an IS (tbdw_time.an)

HIERARCHY h1

(
 zi CHILD OF
 saptamana CHILD OF
 luna CHILD OF
 an
)

HIERARCHY h2

(
 zi CHILD OF
 luna CHILD OF
 trimestru CHILD OF
 semestru CHILD OF
 an);

Se executa validarea obiectului de tip dimensiune pentru tabelul "Time"

```
execute dbms_dimension.validate_dimension(upper('tbw_dim_time'),false,true,'st_tbw_dim_time');
```


Se verifica daca datele din tabelul "Time" indeplinesc constrangerile impuse de obiectul dimensiune definit.

```
SELECT * FROM dimension_exceptions WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbw_dim_time';
```

Query Builder

```
SELECT * FROM dimension_exceptions WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_time';
```

STATEMENT_ID	OWNER	TABLE_NAME	DIMENSION_NAME	RELATIONSHIP	BAD_ROWID	
1	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA4
2	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA5
3	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA6
4	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA7
5	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA8
6	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA9
7	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA0
8	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA1
9	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA2
10	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA3
11	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA4
12	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA5
13	st_tbdw_dim_time	SYS	TBDW_TIME	TBDW_DIM_TIME	CHILD OF	AAAR2hAA8AAAd+JAA6

```
SELECT * FROM tbdw_time
WHERE rowid IN (SELECT bad_rowid
FROM dimension_exceptions
WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_time');
```

Query Builder

```
SELECT * FROM tbdw_time
WHERE rowid IN (SELECT bad_rowid
FROM dimension_exceptions
WHERE statement_id = 'st_tbdw_dim_time');
```

TEMP_ID	AN	SEMESTRU	TRIMESTRU	LUNA	SAPTAMANA_AN	SAPTAMANA_LUNA	ZI_AN	ZI_LUNA	ZI_SAPTAMANA	ZI_NLME	LUNA_NUME	WEEKEND	AN_BISECT	SAPTAMANA_CALENDAR	SAPTAMANA
1	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
2	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
3	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
4	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
5	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
6	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
7	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
8	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
9	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
10	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
11	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1
12	01-JAN-64	1964	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	WEDNESDAY	JANUARY	0	1	1

Se observa ca datele din tabelul "TIME" nu respecta constrangerile impuse de obiectul dimensiune definit.

2.8 Definirea partițiilor; definirea cererilor SQL însoțite de planul de execuție al acestora din care să reiasă ca optimizorul utilizează eficient partițiile

2.8.1 Exemplu partitionare de tip “Range”

Definirea partitiei

```
CREATE TABLE tbdw_sessions_partition_last_decade
PARTITION BY RANGE(start_time_id)
(
PARTITION sessions_2015
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2015','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2016
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2016','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2017
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2017','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2018
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2018','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2019
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2019','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2020
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2020','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2021
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2021','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2022
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2022','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2023
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2023','DD/MM/YYYY')),
PARTITION sessions_2024
VALUES LESS THAN(TO_DATE('31/12/2024','DD/MM/YYYY')))
AS
SELECT *
FROM tbdw_sessions_history
WHERE start_time_id >= TO_DATE('01/01/2015','DD/MM/YYYY')
AND start_time_id < TO_DATE('31/12/2024','DD/MM/YYYY');
```


Verificam costul interogarii fara utilizarea partitiei

```

EXPLAIN PLAN
SET STATEMENT_ID = 'st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp'
FOR
select tb2.an, count(tb1.id) from tbdw_sessions_history tb1, tbdw_time tb2
where tb2.an < 2025
AND tb2.an > 2014
AND tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
group by tb2.an
order by tb2.an asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table','st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp','serial'));
  
```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays the following SQL query:

```

EXPLAIN PLAN
SET STATEMENT_ID = 'st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp'
FOR
select tb2.an, count(tb1.id) from tbdw_sessions_history tb1, tbdw_time tb2
where tb2.an < 2025
AND tb2.an > 2014
AND tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
group by tb2.an
order by tb2.an asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan table','st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_temp','serial'));

```

The execution plan output is as follows:

```

PLAN_TABLE_OUTPUT
-----
1 Plan hash value: 1277050673
2
3
4 | Id | Operation | Name | Rows | Bytes | Cost (CPU%) | Time |
5 -----
6 | 0 | SELECT STATEMENT | | 10 | 330 | 2625 (4) | 00:00:01 |
7 | 1 | SORT GROUP BY | | 10 | 330 | 2625 (4) | 00:00:01 |
8 |* 2 | HASH JOIN | | 6984 | 225K | 2623 (4) | 00:00:01 |
9 | 3 | VIEW | VW_GBF_7 | 6984 | 143K | 1160 (7) | 00:00:01 |
10 | 4 | HASH GROUP BY | | 6984 | 55872 | 1160 (7) | 00:00:01 |
11 | 5 | TABLE ACCESS FULL | TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY | 765K | 5982K | 1108 (2) | 00:00:01 |
12 |* 6 | TABLE ACCESS FULL | TBDW_TIME | 87805 | 1028K | 1462 (1) | 00:00:01 |
13 -----
14
15 Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```

Plan hash value: 1277050673

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		10	330	2625 (4)	00:00:01
1	SORT GROUP BY		10	330	2625 (4)	00:00:01
* 2	HASH JOIN		6984	225K	2623 (4)	00:00:01
3	VIEW	VW_GBF_7	6984	143K	1160 (7)	00:00:01
4	HASH GROUP BY		6984	55872	1160 (7)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	765K	5982K	1108 (2)	00:00:01
* 6	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_TIME	87805	1028K	1462 (1)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```

2 - access("ITEM_1"="TB2"."TIMP_ID")
6 - filter("TB2"."AN">2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2025)

```

Verificam costul interogarii utilizand partitia

```

EXPLAIN PLAN
SET STATEMENT_ID = 'st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_part_temp'
FOR
select tb2.an, count(tb1.id) from tbdw_sessions_partition_last_decade tb1, tbdw_time tb2
where tb2.an < 2025
AND tb2.an > 2014
AND tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
group by tb2.an
order by tb2.an asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan table','st_tbdw_ses_his_dec_part_temp','serial'));

```


Plan hash value: 2629054689

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time	Pstart	Pstop
0	SELECT STATEMENT		10	320	1882 (3)	00:00:01		
1	SORT GROUP BY		10	320	1882 (3)	00:00:01		
* 2	HASH JOIN		2449	78368	1881 (2)	00:00:01		
3	VIEW	VW_GBF_7	2449	48980	418 (6)	00:00:01		
4	HASH GROUP BY		2449	17143	418 (6)	00:00:01		
5	PARTITION RANGE ALL		273K	1873K	400 (2)	00:00:01	1	10
6	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_PARTITION_LAST_DECADE	273K	1873K	400 (2)	00:00:01	1	10
* 7	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_TIME	87805	1028K	1462 (1)	00:00:01		

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

```

2 - access("ITEM_1"="TB2"."TIMP_ID")
7 - filter("TB2"."AN">2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2025)

```

Se poate observa faptul ca utilizarea partitiei a scazut costul de la 2625 la 1882.

2.9 Optimizarea cererii SQL propusă în etapa de analiză

2.9.1 planul de execuție ales de optimizorul bazat pe cost (explicație etape parcurse)

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

2.9.2 sugestii de optimizare a cererii, specificând planul de execuție obținut

Această secțiune este rezervată dezvoltărilor viitoare. Versiunea actuală reflectă stadiul proiectului la momentul depunerii sale academice inițiale.

2.10 Crearea rapoartelor cu complexitate diferită (la acest nivel vor fi scripturi SQL, fără reprezentare grafică)

2.10.1 Exemplul 1

Sa se verifice daca capacitatea locatiilor a fost depasita. Daca aceasta a fost depasita, sa se afiseze, ziua in care a fost depasita, numele locatiei, judetul, si numarul de sesiuni inregistrate in ziua respectiva. Sa se ordoneze rezultatele in functie de adresa, judet, data si capacitate. Sa se determine costul interogarii.

Verific capacitatea locatiilor.

```
select id, address, capacity from tbdw_locations order by capacity asc;
```


The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane is open, showing a tree view of the database schema. The 'Tables (Filtered)' section is expanded, showing a list of tables including TB_CITIES, TB_CONTRACTS, TB_CUSTOMERS, TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_LOCATIONS, TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TBW_CUSTOMERS, TBW_LOCATIONS, TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY, TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY, TBW_TIME, TBW_TRAINERS, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, and TBE_LAST_NAMES. The 'Query Builder' pane in the center contains the following SQL query:

```
1 select id, address, capacity from tbdw_locations order by capacity asc;
```

Below the query, the 'Query Result' pane displays the results of the query. The results are shown in a table with columns ID, ADDRESS, and CAPACITY. The table contains 13 rows of data:

ID	ADDRESS	CAPACITY
1	23 address81564	50
2	67 address33794	50
3	5 address45313	53
4	35 address95923	54
5	63 address53055	54
6	14 address48345	54
7	27 address80609	54
8	29 address78826	54
9	47 address34486	55
10	16 address81038	55
11	4 address75448	55
12	53 address84834	56
13	15 address22078	57

Observ ca locatiile au o capacitate destul de ridicata. Reduc capacitatea locatiilor pentru a demonstra functionalitatea scripturilor.

```
update tbdw_locations set capacity = capacity - 40;
```

Execut scriptul pentru cerinta.

```

Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.address,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;

```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The Query Builder window displays the following SQL query:

```

1 Select
2   tb2.start_time_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
3 From
4   tbdw_sessions_history tb2
5 JOIN
6   tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
7 Group By
8   tb1.address,
9   tb1.state_name,
10  tb2.start_time_id,
11  tb1.capacity
12 Having
13   count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;
14

```

The Query Result window shows the following data:

START_TIME_ID	ADDRESS	STATE_NAME	NUMBER_OF_SESSIONS	CAPACITY
132 28-MAR-16	address81564	Neamt	11	10
133 17-OCT-09	address81564	Neamt	11	10
134 07-MAY-17	address81564	Neamt	11	10
135 13-OCT-15	address81564	Neamt	12	10
136 19-FEB-08	address33794	Constanta	11	10
137 06-NOV-22	address33794	Constanta	20	10
138 03-MAY-03	address34486	Dolj	16	15
139 30-OCT-22	address33794	Constanta	11	10
140 31-JUL-08	address78826	Prahova	15	14
141 07-JUN-00	address81564	Neamt	11	10
142 27-JUL-08	address33794	Constanta	11	10
143 07-FEB-23	address33794	Constanta	11	10

Verific costul.

```

explain plan
set statement_id = 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_1'
for
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.address,

```

```

tb1.state_name,
tb2.start_time_id,
tb1.capacity
Having
count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_1','serial'));

```


Plan hash value: 902696625

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		621K	182M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 1	FILTER					
2	HASH GROUP BY		621K	182M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 3	HASH JOIN		621K	182M	1114 (2)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBW_LOCATIONS	70	20020	3 (0)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	621K	13M	1106 (2)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

- 1 - filter("TB1"."CAPACITY"<COUNT(*))
- 3 - access("TB2"."LOCATION_ID"="TB1"."LOCATION_ID")

Note

- dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)

Observ costul tranzactiei fiind "1156".

Sa se modifice cererea anterioara astfel incat sa se afiseze locatiile in care capacitatea a fost depasita cu minim 50%. Datele vor fi ordonate in functie de locatie.

```
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.location_id,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
Order by
  tb1.location_id asc;
```


The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The 'Connections' pane on the left shows the database structure, including tables like TB_SESSIONS and TB_LOCATIONS. The main window shows a SQL query in the 'Worksheet' pane, which is identical to the one provided in the text above. Below the query, the 'Query Result' pane shows the output of the query, displaying 9 rows of data. The columns are START_TIME_ID, LOCATION_ID, STATE_NAME, NUMBER_OF_SESSIONS, and CAPACITY. The data shows that for location 67 (Constanta), the number of sessions (20) exceeds the capacity (10) by more than 50%.

START_TIME_ID	LOCATION_ID	STATE_NAME	NUMBER_OF_SESSIONS	CAPACITY
1 07-DEC-16	4	Iasi	23	15
2 26-AUG-06	23	Neamt	16	10
3 15-OCT-22	23	Neamt	17	10
4 25-MAR-02	67	Constanta	18	10
5 31-JUL-03	67	Constanta	16	10
6 07-DEC-06	67	Constanta	16	10
7 28-JAN-18	67	Constanta	17	10
8 12-MAY-19	67	Constanta	16	10
9 06-NOV-22	67	Constanta	20	10

Verific costul.

```
explain plan
set statement_id = 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_2'
for
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions, tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locatons tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.location_id,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
Order by
  tb1.location_id asc;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_2', 'serial'));
```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The left pane shows the database schema with tables like TB_CITIES, TB_CONTRACTS, TB_CUSTOMERS, TB_CUSTOMERS_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_LOCATIONS, TB_RESULTS, TB_SESSIONS, TB_STATES, TB_SUBSCRIPTIONS, TB_TRAINERS, TBW_CUSTOMERS, TBW_LOCATIONS_HISTORY, TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY, TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY, TBW_TIME, TBW_TRAINERS, TBE_FIRST_NAMES, TBE_HEALTH, and TBE_LAST_NAMES. The main window shows the SQL query and its explain plan.

```
1 SELECT plan_table_output
2 FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_loc_cap_request_1_2', 'serial'));
```

Script Output x Explain Plan x Query Result x
All Rows Fetched: 22 in 0.774 seconds

PLAN_TABLE_OUTPUT

```
1 Plan hash value: 2247675393
2
3
4 | Id | Operation | Name | Rows | Bytes | Cost (%CPU) | Time |
5 -----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|-----|
6 | 0 | SELECT STATEMENT | | | 621K | 105M | 1156 (6) | 00:00:01 |
7 | * | 1 | FILTER | | | | | |
8 | 2 | SORT GROUP BY | | | 621K | 105M | 1156 (6) | 00:00:01 |
9 | * | 3 | HASH JOIN | | 621K | 105M | 1114 (2) | 00:00:01 |
10 | 4 | TABLE ACCESS FULL | TBW_LOCATIONS | 70 | 10920 | 3 (0) | 00:00:01 |
11 | 5 | TABLE ACCESS FULL | TBW_SESSIONS_HISTORY | 621K | 13M | 1106 (2) | 00:00:01 |
12
13
14 Predicate Information (identified by operation id):
15 -----|-----|-----|-----|
16
17 1 - filter(COUNT(*)>'TB1"."CAPACITY'+'TB1"."CAPACITY"/2)
18 3 - access("TB2"."LOCATION_ID"="TB1"."LOCATION_ID")
19
20 Note
21 ----
22 - dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)
```

Plan hash value: 2247675393

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		621K	105M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 1	FILTER					
2	SORT GROUP BY		621K	105M	1156 (6)	00:00:01
* 3	HASH JOIN		621K	105M	1114 (2)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_LOCATIONS	70	10920	3 (0)	00:00:01
5	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBDW_SESSIONS_HISTORY	621K	13M	1106 (2)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

- 1 - filter(COUNT(*)>"TB1"."CAPACITY"+"TB1"."CAPACITY"/2)
- 3 - access("TB2"."LOCATION_ID"="TB1"."LOCATION_ID")

Note

- dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)

Observ costul tranzactiei fiind "1156".

Pentru locatiile obtinute la punctul anterior sa se determine daca exista un trend ascendent in ultimii 5 ani de zile de crestere al numarului de sesiuni. Sa se ordoneze rezultatele in functie de locatie, an, numarul de sesiuni din anul respectiv.

Voi utiliza un materialized view pentru a stoca rezultatele de la cerinta anterioara.

```
CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW tbdw_mv_locations_overflow_capacity1
BUILD IMMEDIATE
REFRESH COMPLETE
ON DEMAND
AS
Select
  tb2.start_time_id, tb1.location_id, tb1.address, tb1.state_name, count(tb2.id) AS number_of_sessions,
  tb1.capacity
From
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2
JOIN
  tbdw_locations tb1 on tb2.location_id = tb1.location_id
Group By
  tb1.location_id,
  tb1.address,
  tb1.state_name,
  tb2.start_time_id,
  tb1.capacity
Having
  count(tb2.id) > tb1.capacity + (tb1.capacity/2)
```

Order by
tb1.location_id asc;

3. Sa se calculeze veniturile din ultimii 10 ani de zile. Sa se afiseze anul si suma totala a incasarilor. Sa se ordoneze dupa an, descrescator.

```
select
  tb2.an, sum(tb1.price)
from
  tbdw_subscriptions_history tb1
join
  tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
where
  tb2.an >= 2014
and
  tb2.an < 2024
group by
  tb2.an
order by
  tb2.an;
```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, a tree view displays the database schema, including tables like TB_CITIES, TB_CONTRACTS, TB_CUSTOMERS, and TBW_TIME. The main window shows a SQL query in the Worksheet:

```

1 select
2   tb2.an, sum(tb1.price)
3 from
4   tbdw_subscriptions_history tb1
5 join
6   tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
7 where
8   tb2.an >= 2014
9 and
10  tb2.an < 2024
11 group by
12  tb2.an
13 order by

```

Below the query, the Query Results window displays the following data:

AN	SUM(TB1.PRICE)
1 2014	475180
2 2015	449985
3 2016	462840
4 2017	470860
5 2018	472765
6 2019	430540
7 2020	436650
8 2021	469045
9 2022	493740
10 2023	53010

Verific costul.

```

explain plan
set statement_id = 'dw_income_request_3'
for
select
  tb2.an, sum(tb1.price)
from
  tbdw_subscriptions_history tb1
join
  tbdw_time tb2 on tb1.start_time_id = tb2.timp_id
where
  tb2.an >= 2014
and
  tb2.an < 2024
group by
  tb2.an
order by
  tb2.an;

SELECT plan_table_output
FROM table(dbms_xplan.display('plan_table', 'dw_income_request_3', 'serial'));

```


Plan hash value: 647554590

Id	Operation	Name	Rows	Bytes	Cost (%CPU)	Time
0	SELECT STATEMENT		14806	636K	28 (11)	00:00:01
1	SORT GROUP BY		14806	636K	28 (11)	00:00:01
2	NESTED LOOPS		14806	636K	27 (8)	00:00:01
3	NESTED LOOPS		14806	636K	27 (8)	00:00:01
4	TABLE ACCESS FULL	TBW_SUBSCRIPTIONS_HISTORY	14806	318K	25 (0)	00:00:01
* 5	INDEX UNIQUE SCAN	TBW_TIME_ID_PK	1		0 (0)	00:00:01
* 6	TABLE ACCESS BY INDEX ROWID	TBW_TIME	1	22	0 (0)	00:00:01

Predicate Information (identified by operation id):

- 5 - access("TB1"."START_TIME_ID"="TB2"."TIME_ID")
- 6 - filter("TB2"."AN">=2014 AND "TB2"."AN"<2024)

Note

- dynamic statistics used: dynamic sampling (level=2)

Observa costul tranzactiei fiind "28".

2.10.2 Exemplul 2

Sa se afiseze numarul de clienti care prefera sesiuni de antrenament cu antrenori de sex masculin si numarul de clienti care prefera sesiuni de antrenament cu antrenori de sex feminin.

Utilizez un **materialized view** pentru a contoriza numarul de sesiuni realizate cu un antrenor masculin pentru fiecare utilizator.

```
CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW tbdw_mv_customers_prefered_trainer_male
BUILD IMMEDIATE
REFRESH COMPLETE
ON DEMAND
AS
select
  tb1.id, count(tb3.gender) as prefered_trainer_male
from
  tbdw_customers tb1
join
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2 on tb1.customer_id = tb2.customer_id
join
  tbdw_trainers tb3 on tb2.trainer_id = tb3.trainer_id
where
  tb3.gender = 'male'
group by
  tb1.id
order by
  tb1.id;
```


Utilizaz un **materialized view** pentru a contoriza numarul de sesiuni realizate cu un antrenor feminin pentru fiecare utilizator.

```
CREATE MATERIALIZED VIEW tbdw_mv_customers_prefered_trainer_female2
BUILD IMMEDIATE
REFRESH COMPLETE
ON DEMAND
AS
select
  tb1.id, count(tb3.gender) as prefered_trainer_female
from
  tbdw_customers tb1
join
  tbdw_sessions_history tb2 on tb1.customer_id = tb2.customer_id
join
  tbdw_trainers tb3 on tb2.trainer_id = tb3.trainer_id
where
  tb3.gender = 'female'
group by
  tb1.id
order by
  tb1.id;
```


Utilizaz o procedura care utilizeaza cele doua view-uri definite anterior pentru a calcula numarul de clienti care prefera sesiuni de antrenament cu antrenori de sex masculin si numarul de clienti care prefera sesiuni de antrenament cu antrenori de sex feminin.

Am fost inclus deasemenea si numarul de clienti care au acelasi numar de sesiuni indiferent de sexul antrenorilor.

```
CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_customers_preferred_trainer AS
  min_id number;
  max_id number;
  pf_male number;
  pf_female number;
  pf_male_total number;
  pf_female_total number;
  pf_equal_total number;
BEGIN
  BEGIN
    SELECT min(customer_id) into min_id FROM tbdw_customers;
    SELECT max(customer_id) into max_id FROM tbdw_customers;
  EXCEPTION
    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
      min_id := 0;
      max_id := 0;
  END;
END;
```

```

pf_male_total :=0;
pf_female_total :=0;
pf_equal_total :=0;

for contor in min_id..max_id
Loop
  BEGIN
  SELECT
    preferred_trainer_female into pf_female
  FROM
    tbdw_mv_customers_prefered_trainer_female2 tb1
  WHERE
    tb1.id = contor;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    pf_female := 0;
  END;

  BEGIN
  SELECT
    preferred_trainer_male into pf_male
  FROM
    tbdw_mv_customers_prefered_trainer_male tb1
  WHERE
    tb1.id = contor;
  EXCEPTION
  WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
    pf_male := 0;
  END;

  if pf_male > pf_female then pf_male_total := pf_male_total+1; end if;
  if pf_male < pf_female then pf_female_total := pf_female_total+1; end if;
  if pf_male = pf_female then pf_equal_total := pf_equal_total+1; end if;

end Loop;

dbms_output.put_line ('Number of customers who prefer male trainers ' || pf_male_total);
dbms_output.put_line ('Number of customers who prefer female trainers ' || pf_female_total);
dbms_output.put_line ('Number of customers neutral ' || pf_equal_total);
END;
/
set serveroutput on;
begin
tbdw_customers_prefered_trainer;
end;
/

```

The screenshot displays the Oracle SQL Developer environment. On the left, the 'Connections' pane shows a tree view of database objects under 'DW_PROJECT3.1', including tables like TB_CITIES, TB_CONTRACTS, TB_CUSTOMERS, and TB_TRAINERS. The main workspace is titled 'Worksheet' and contains a PL/SQL procedure definition:

```
1 CREATE or REPLACE PROCEDURE tbdw_customers_prefered_trainer AS
2   min_id number;
3   max_id number;
4   pf_male number;
5   pf_female number;
6   pf_male_total number;
7   pf_female_total number;
8   pf_equal_total number;
9 BEGIN
10  BEGIN
11    SELECT min(customer_id) into min_id FROM tbdw_customers;
12    SELECT max(customer_id) into max_id FROM tbdw_customers;
13  EXCEPTION
14    WHEN NO_DATA_FOUND THEN
15      min_id := 0;
16      max_id := 0;
```

Below the code editor, the 'Script Output' pane shows the message: 'Procedure TBDW_CUSTOMERS_PREFERRED_TRAINER compiled'. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'Task completed in 0.895 seconds'.

Dupa rularea procedurii am urmatoarele rezultate.

“Number of customers who prefer male trainers 3017”

“Number of customers who prefer female trainers 632”

“Number of customers neutral 223”

Din rezultate observ ca predominant clientii au ales antrenori de sex masculine.